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CHAPTER 1: USER EXPERIENCE (UX)

UX, or *User Experience*, in a nutshell is the quality of the experience a person has when interacting with a specific product.

1.1. Introduction

The term was originally used in reference to human-computer interactions and is still widely associated with these disciplines. The term is now used to refer to any specific interaction between humans and design, ranging from a digital device, to a sales process, to an entire conference.

Perhaps due to its organic development and lack of formalisation, *User Experience* can be defined differently according to different departments within an organisation: in some organisations, it is owned by *marketing*; in others, it falls under *Information Technology* (abbreviated IT).

Thus, from a solution perspective, some organisations base their *user experience* around academic and research approaches of *human-computer* interaction (HCI for short); others consider *interface* and *product design*, while still others let this be driven by *marketing* or IT.

1.2. A Brief History

An early example of the use of the word *User Experience* appeared in the title of an article '*User Experience With the CYBER Graphics Terminal*'¹. Subsequently, there were numerous other examples of 'User Experience' in use

¹ E. C. EDWARDS, D. J. KASIK, *User Experience With the CYBER Graphics Terminal*, in AA.VV., *VIM-21 Proceedings Twenty-First Semi-Annual Vim: Conference October 13-17, Denver Colorado, 1974*.

in the late 1970s and early 1980s, largely confined to human-computer interaction communities and particularly in the context of *User-Centred Design* (UCD for short).

We can find a description of the term approaching its modern meaning in a book on human-computer interaction from the mid-1980s:

*"This section of the book contains chapters that get directly at the question of the quality of the user's experience. This is of course the ultimate criterion of User Centered System Design, but most workers approach it obliquely in various ways such as exploring the implementation techniques, or applying existing cognitive approaches"*².

Finally, Donald Norman, a sociologist, ergonomist and prominent person in the HCI community and then an executive for *Apple Computer Inc.* made the term *User Experience* famous worldwide when he awarded himself the title of *User Experience Architect* in 1993. Thanks to Norman's status as a *leader* in the HCI community, this unconventional title raised awareness of the term.

The term, first introduced by Norman in the late 1980s, initially referred to the need to 'design for' the user, i.e. that part of the designer to adopt a perspective and point of view that was not his own, but that of the end user of the product in question.

Over the years, the approach has become a true methodology, which will be explained in the following chapters, and has extended the concept of user-centred and human-centred to the design process itself: no longer just designing for the user then, but also co-designing with the user.

1.3. Development

In the mid-1990s, many technology companies used the term to represent a commitment to and focus on human-human interactions.

² D. A. NORMAN, S. DRAPER, *User Centered System Design: New Perspectives on Human-Computer Interaction* Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, 1986, p. 64.

superior computers as a key element in the difference of the product. While the *dot.com* technology boom, which peaked in 2000, numerous books were published that included *User Experience* in the title, these books focused almost exclusively on *web design* elements.

During its rise in *User Experience* in the 1990s it suffered confusion due to the popularity of two other similar terms, *User-Centred Design* and *Experience Design*. Over time, UCD has been further clarified as a specific process and approach to product design, while Experience Design has largely shifted to describe a hybrid design discipline that focuses on environmental and multisensory design, particularly in the context of digital displays and installations.

1.4. Current status

In recent years, *User Experience* has transcended simple interactions within IT environments and is used as a qualifier for various online and offline experiences, ranging from person-to-person interactions, such as customer service, as well as analogue products such as cars. Many companies today have *User Experience* teams and departments and the term has taken on a broader meaning. An industry association, the *User Experience Network* (abbreviated UXnet), has long been dedicated to promoting this discipline, and currently one of the most authoritative sources in the field is the *Interaction Design Foundation*³, of which Donald Norman is a member of the *executive board* of the foundation, among other prominent personalities.

During an interview two years after the launch of the iPod, Steve Jobs asserted that many people make the mistake of thinking that *design* is only what 'you see':

³ The *Interaction Design Foundation* (abbreviated IDF) is an independent *nonprofit* foundation that, collaborating with leading universities such as Stanford, Cambridge and top companies, aims to diffuse high-quality education in a way that is accessible to many. The IDF draws its inspiration from the Scandinavian educational model, which leaves a great deal of autonomy to the student in organising teaching. The foundation also supports collaboration and the creation of a large *community* that currently numbers more than 400 local groups in 97 countries.

"People think it's this veneer that the designers are handed this box and told, 'Make it look good!' That's not what we think design is. It's not just what it looks like and feels like. Design is how it works⁴."

This emblematic phrase '*design is how it works*', which was a far cry from what was for many, mistakenly, considered a cornerstone of the company with the *bitten apple*, or rather the aesthetic aspect, marked time and revealed to the general public the approach of *industrial design* (ID for short), of which there has been ample academic documentation since the mid-20th century, to newer concepts such as interaction and user satisfaction, concepts that can be linked to the branch of knowledge known as *User Experience*.

User experience has thus evolved from HCI to broader issues that affect the user and determine the competitive difference of a product, suggesting that it will remain a relevant issue for design and business in the future.

1.5. UX in the *mobile* environment

The advancement of mobile technologies, marked by the launch of the first iPhone in 2007, has driven growth in the *smartphone* market, a market to 366.3⁵ million units per year. The subsequent creation of the App Store, the Apple's signature *marketplace* for mobile applications that work with Cupertino-designed devices, and the development of similar solutions by competitors has led to the simplification of application marketing (a word often abbreviated using the neologism *app*⁶), making it easy to reach a very large audience in a very short time, and the development of

⁴ R. WALKER, *The Guts of a New Machine* in *New York Times* (30 November 2003), p. 78.

⁵ B. SIMONETTA, *Smartphones, the market is growing again. And Huawei advances despite Trump*, in *Il Sole 24 Ore* (1 November 2019).

⁶ "*app s. f. inv. Computer application. [...] From the English app, shortening of application ('computer application')*" s.v. "app", in AA. VV., *The Treccani Vocabulary, 'Neologisms'*, 2014.

Increasingly simple programming languages, coupled with the creation of IDEs⁷ that help the developer a lot, have made app development accessible also to individuals, young students and generally to everyone. The number of apps available on the main stores has always increased, by way of example, at the launch of the App Store there were only 500 apps, which then increased to 300,000⁸ in 2010, and now exceeds 4 million⁹.

However, many of the apps on the market suffer a poor user experience. Of the 4 million apps available, a small percentage realise more than 90 per cent of the 170 billion annual *downloads*. According to research by the Politecnico di Milano, on average, a user has downloaded around 22 apps onto his or her device and effectively uses only 12 of them, a number that is already low and drops even further to 9 if one considers the programmes launched in the last month, and on average only⁴¹⁰ are used in a day. For this reason, the subject of *user experience in the area of mobile applications*, especially for large *publishers*, is very much on the agenda nowadays.

1.5.1. A look back, the Game Boy case

Let us now take a step back to 1989, when the term *smartphone* had not yet been coined and the world saw the release of Nokia's first mobile phone, the *Mobira Cityman900*. A device weighing close to 0.8 *kg* and with a price (updated to today's value) approaching 10,000 euros.

At that time, three companies, Nintendo, Sega and Atari, released portable game consoles. The first of their kind. Hand-held consoles redefined the paradigm of gaming *software fruition*, moving from static home use to dynamic use during the commute to work or outdoors, and were

⁷ An *integrated development environment* (IDE), also integrated design environment and integrated *debugging* environment, respectively), in computer science, is *software* that, in the programming phase, supports programmers in developing the source code of a programme.

⁸ C. BARBATO, *The App Store reaches 300,000 apps*, (www.melamorsicata.it) [last accessed 16.02.2020].

⁹ R. COWLEY, *Count of Active Applications in the App Store* (www.pocketgamer.biz) [last accessed 16.02.2020].

¹⁰ S. COSIMI, *There are 2 million apps, why do we use four?* (www.esquire.com) [last accessed 17.02.2020].

products that had to take the issue of user experience seriously.

Nintendo released the *Game Boy*, Atari soon after the *Lynx* and Sega released the *Game Gear* the following year. Both the *Lynx* and *Game Gear* had backlit screens with a palette of 4096 colours. The *Game Boy* had a black and white display with just four shades of grey on a greenish, non-backlit screen. The *Game Gear* and *Lynx* had large, ergonomic handles with which the user could hold the mobile device and control the buttons, the *Game Boy* was unergonomic and tiny.

Based on these technical specifications, it causes some surprise to discover that Nintendo's console sold 180.7 million units and was sold for an impressive 14 years, while Atari's *console* sold just 3 million units in 5 years and Sega's 10.5 million units in 7 years.

The *Game Boy* device's planetary success is neither accidental nor fortuitous, but the result of precise choices made during the design phase taking into account the potential user experience a typical purchaser of their product would have.

The Nintendo development team eliminated everything superfluous by making the *Game Boy*. They used an old Sharp processor from the 1970s. They made it as small as possible, the screen did not use colours, but in return it was cheaper than its competitors, it was sold at an affordable price of \$90 compared to the \$150 of *Game Gear* and \$180 of *Lynx*. The *Big Enne* device was small enough to fit inside the back of a pair of trousers. It was not as ergonomic as its *competitors'* devices, but the layout of the buttons allowed good control and to stand with your elbows not too wide during gaming sessions (which is useful if you think about using it on a bus or train), it was also basically indestructible, it easily withstood falls and even tolerated water, and to top it off the Nintendo handheld *console* allowed up to 30 hours of play on just two 'stylus' batteries. Both the *Game Gear* and the *Lynx* required as many as six 'stylus' batteries and provided just 3-5 hours of use.

Gunpei Yokoi, then in charge of the *Game Boy* project, said during an interview shortly before his death that at Nintendo they were pushing for colour graphics in their mobile device, but he lobbied to have the

monochrome screen saying '*Once you start playing the game, the colours aren't important. You get drawn, mentally, into the world of the game*¹¹'. Yokoi was someone who fully understood the user experience, he understood that the most important thing was to engage the user and make them feel emotions, but to do this he had to find a compromise, he could not make a cheap *console* that also had a backlit colour screen but at the same time was small and had a long battery life. Considering the user context, he realised that long battery life, durability and a small *form factor* of the device would provide a greater user experience than a colour screen and a cutting-edge spec sheet. The results proved him right.

1.5.2. Conclusions

After this interlude in the 1980s, we return to the current situation where millions of apps are available, but only very few manage to provide a polished and satisfying user experience, and therefore only very few apps become commonplace and find the approval of the general public. This is because most of these apps, such as Sega and Atari devices, were not designed with *user experience* as a fundamental parameter. Therefore, large companies are paying increasing attention to UX issues, so much so that they are setting up teams dedicated to research and development on these issues and integrating them more and more into the development process, from *Idea Generation* and then along the entire chain up to the *Software Developing* phase and final *testing*.

Emerging companies and *start-ups*, enjoying a generally more organic and less bureaucratic structure, tend to require *UX skills* in many corporate roles and figures involved in the development process with hybrid titles such as *UI / UX Designer* or *Product Design / UX Designer* are quite common.

¹¹ G. YOKOI, in Y. MORIKAWA, *Console Gaming Then and Now Developer Interview*, 1997.

CHAPTER 2: INTERACTION DESIGN (IXD)

IxD, or *Interaction Design*, is the art of facilitating interactions between human beings through products and services.

2.1 Introduction

Interaction Design is an applied art ¹²; its usefulness can be seen in its application to real problems, such as figuring out the best way to send an *email*. Many times *Interaction Design* is invisible, it works behind the scenes. An example is the *Windows* and *macOS* desktop operating systems, which basically do the same thing but give us a different feeling. This is because *Interaction Design* is about behaviour, and behaviour is much more difficult to observe and understand than appearance.

It is much easier to notice and discuss a flashy colour than an imperceptible transaction that can, over time, drive us mad. *Interaction Designers are designers* and have the following *dictates*:

- **focus on users**, users are interested in performing their tasks and achieve their goals within their limits; *designers* are advocates for end users;
- **finding alternatives**, *design* means "creating a third opinion";
- **use conceptualisation and prototyping**, solutions are found, *designers* build models for testing. Each prototype represents only one of the possible solutions, several prototypes need to be created to arrive at a single final product;
- **collaborate and afford constraints**, *designers* rarely have paper white to be able to do what they want, indeed, they have to respond to *business*, making compromises with colleagues and meeting deadlines;

¹² "*applied art s. f. plural applied arts. [...] when the creative process is not an end in itself but is aimed at the production of objects for use*" s.v. "applied arts", in A. M. PIRAS, *Treccani Italian Encyclopaedia*, "VII Appendix", 2006.

- **create appropriate solutions**, *designers* bring with them their experience that grows from one project to the next, but a solution may not be used in other contexts. One has to create appropriate solutions only for a particular context at a particular time (a modern-day example is given by *Amazon*);

- **draw on a wide range of influences**, each *designer* has a broad spectrum from which to draw aspirations and solutions;

- **incorporate emotion** into *design*, products without an emotional component communicate nothing to people. Emotion is a fundamental component of the process and must be considered in *design* decisions.

2.2A Brief History

IxD probably began with the American Indians when they used smoke signals for long-distance communication, then with the Celts who used stone mounds to communicate the weather.

In the 1930s, Samuel Morse created a system for transforming simple electromagnetic impulses into a coded language for communicating words over long distances; in the years that followed, the *Morse* code and the telegraph became different throughout the world, as did the entire system for using it.

Other mass communication tools also required design engineers, where interfaces and systems were needed not only for the receivers (telephones, radio, television) but also for the devices used to create and send messages (telephone switchboards, microphones, cameras)

Of great importance was the first generation of computers (ENIAC) a result of engineering, not just *design*. Humans had to adapt to use them, not vice versa, and that means speaking the language of machines, not our own.

Engineers spent very little energy on *design* to make the first computers more usable. They worked mainly on making them faster and more powerful. It was not until the 1960s that engineers began to focus on people and started to devise new *input* methods.

In 1990, Bill Moggridge, an executive at the *design* firm IDEO, realised that he and his colleagues were creating a very different kind of *design*; it was not product *design even though they were* designing products; it was not communication *design even though they were* using some of the tools of that discipline; it was not even computer science even though they were having a lot to do with computers and *software*. It was something different.

That process came from all those disciplines but, at the same time, it was something to do with connecting people through the products they used.

Moggridge called this new practice *Interaction Design*. In the following years, *Interaction Design* went from a small specialist discipline to a practice implemented by tens of thousands of people worldwide.

As the *internet* matured, so did all technologies. In fact, since the late 1990s, the *internet* has been used to do things like trade stocks, sell things, share photos and much more.

The internet today has become a platform for applications, which can take advantage of the many features that the *internet* offers: such as passive data collection. But not only the *Internet* has changed but also, and more importantly, access to it. Through faster and faster broadband connections and increasingly high-performance *wifi* networks, the types of interactions we have and where we have them have changed. That is why there has never been a better time to be an *interaction designer*.

2.3 The various approaches

When a problem occurs during the design *process* (analysed in detail a few pages further on), the *designer*, after examining it from different angles, can arrive at a solution through four main approaches. It is up to him to choose the most suitable ones.

2.3.1. User-centred design

The philosophy behind this approach is based on this affirmation "users know best ¹³". The people who will use a product or service know their needs, goals and preferences and it is up to the *designer* to discover these things and design for them. You cannot design something without first asking the users. This *design* concept has existed for a long time and has its roots in industrial *design*, ergonomics and the belief that *designers* should adapt products to people and not the other way around. In this approach, designers involve users at every stage of the project: they consult them at the outset to see if the proposal will meet their needs and conduct extensive research to determine what their goals are in the current situation. Then, they develop design-related models or prototypes that will be tested on users.

Advantages

UCD sets itself some really important goals. *Designers* will

THE

UCD ¹⁴

focus on what the user ultimately wants to achieve; it then determines the tasks and means required to achieve those goals, but always bearing in mind the users' needs and preferences.

Disadvantages

In the use of this approach, as we shall see in more detail in the next chapter devoted to it, it is essential to base the analysis on the right type of users because, if one bases the entire analysis on the wrong type of users, the results that would result would be completely misleading.

2.3.2. Activity-centred design

This approach does not focus on goals or user preferences, but precisely on activities. Activities can be the actions performed to

¹³ D. SAFFER, *Interaction Design: intelligent applications and ingenious devices with interaction design*. Ediz. Italiana, Paravia Bruno Mondadori Editori, 2007, p. 31.

¹⁴ An acronym for 'User-Centred Design', derived from the English equivalent *User-Centred Design*.

a purpose, they may be short and simple or time-consuming. Some activities may have a fixed end, others have no fixed end; each activity ends when the actor decides it is finished. Activities are made up of actions and decisions. *Designers* call them tasks. Tasks can consist of a single act such as pressing a button or of more complicated ones. Each task is a moment in the life of an activity. For example, if the task is to make a call, one of the tasks is to find the phone number.

Advantages

Activity-centred design allows designers to focus strictly on the task at hand and create support for the activity instead of more distant goals. It is therefore particularly suitable for complicated actions.

Disadvantages

As in UCD, task-centred design relies on research for insights; *designers* observe and interview users to understand their behaviour rather than their goals. They then catalogue all activities and tasks and then design solutions to help them complete the task, not achieve a goal.

2.3.3. System design

Systems *design* is a very analytical way of solving problems; it uses an established organisation of components to create *design* solutions. A difference of the UCD, where at the centre is the user, here is the system; a set of entities acting on each other. Systems do not have to be *computers*, they can be people, devices, machines. They can be simple, like the domestic heating system, or very complex, like entire governments. In this approach, the emphasis on users diminishes in favour of context. Designers using systems *design* focus on the entire context of use, not just objects or devices.

In a nutshell, it outlines all the components that the system will need, giving *designers* a clear path to follow: a lens, a sensor, a comparator and an actuator.

Advantages

Systems *design* is a very logical and analytical approach to *Interaction Design*. Its strength is its usefulness in seeing the complete picture of the project. This makes it very useful in areas where the understanding of dynamics and flows is highly complex.

Disadvantages

The downside, however, is that emotions, passions and imagination play only a small part in this type of *design*. Which makes it of little use in B2C and *mainstream* contexts.

2.3.4. Design of genius

Genius design only affords itself to the wisdom and experience of the designer ¹⁵. The user is only involved (in some cases) at the end of the project to test whether it really works as intended. This, however, can have its pros and cons.

Advantages

Being an easier approach than the others, genius design is practised even by inexperienced *designers*; it requires much less effort, just sketching on the board rather than carrying out thorough user research. This approach can also be adopted by large companies. *Apple Inc.* for example, preferring not to do user research and testing, perhaps for reasons of trade secret protection, using this approach created an iconic product such as the iPod: one of the most revolutionary and popular innovations ever.

¹⁵ D. SAFFER, *Interaction Design: intelligent applications and ingenious devices with Interaction Design*. Italian ed., Paravia Bruno Mondadori Editori, 2007.

Disadvantages

Such an approach can also lead to great failures and, just to stay in the 'house' of Apple, *one* can cite the great failure of the Newton: the forerunner of the modern *tablet* and unfortunate 'father' of the iPad or the Apple Pippin gaming *console*, which is even listed among the worst technological products in history¹⁶.

2.3.5. Considerations on the four approaches

All four approaches reviewed are used to create successful products, from *websites* to consumer electronics to non-digital services. The best *designers* are those able to move between the approaches, applying the one best suited to the situation and sometimes applying multiple approaches even within the same project.

2.4. The elements of Interaction Design

Regardless of the type of approach used, for *Interaction Design*, the basic notions used in solutions remain the same. Unlike other design disciplines, which use visual elements such as line or 3D shapes, in *Interaction Design* the elements are conceptual. We will now analyse the elements of Interaction Design.

2.4.1 Movement

Movement refers to the behaviour of products in response to the behaviour of people. Movement coloured by attitudes, culture, personality and context. There is a wide variation even in such universal and seemingly simple behaviours as walking (this is why we need running shoes or walkers for the elderly) and the designs we create have to accommodate and respond to these variations. Even a movement as simple as pressing a button can be difficult if you are elderly or

¹⁶ D. TYNAN, *The 25 Worst Tech Products of All Time* (www.pcworld.com) [last accessed 14.04.2020].

disabled. Every movement triggers a reaction (or action *feedback*) so without movement there can be no interaction.

2.4.2 *Space*

Movement takes place in some kind of space. *Interaction Designers* work on both 2D and 3D spaces. Very often, *Interaction Design* involves a combination of physical and digital space, such as turning the knob on the stereo, or turning the *digital crown* on the Apple Watch. One feature that *Interaction Designers* very often underuse is what Renaissance painters discovered long ago, namely perspective. Objects can give the impression of moving back and forth even in a 2D space as if they were in a 3D one. A concept that is sorely lacking in *websites* and rarely applied in *non-gaming apps*.

Space therefore provides a context for movement, whether physical or digital. The resulting movement and action that we want to analyse can take place anywhere in these spaces and the *designer* must take this into account.

2.4.3. *Time*

All interactions take place in a space, but also in time. Sometimes an interaction may occur instantaneously, such as a mouse click or *swipe gesture*, other times it may take longer.

"Completing a movement through space takes time.

Interaction Designers must be time-conscious. Some tasks are complicated and it takes a long time to complete them, e.g. searching for and buying a product. It would be a bad thing if *Amazon* or *eBay* would make the session expire after a few minutes by requiring you to register again. Surely we could make a distinction between digital time and the time perceived by human beings. Digital time is measured in milliseconds: the changes that can be made by a PC can be almost instantaneous, to the point of forcing the

programmers to add voluntary pauses so that users have time to interact. An excessive delay, an unjustified wait, however, can conversely create a situation of frustration, anger.

Time creates rhythm, and *Interaction Designers* control that too; the speed at which a folder is opened or closed, how slowly a drop-down menu should open. Battery life is another time element that *designers* need to be aware of.

2.4.4. Visual appearance

The visual appearance of an object gives us clues about how the object behaves and how we should interact with that object. It is an important source of what cognitive psychologist James Gibson, from his early studies back in 1966, called *affordance*. Gibson later explored this concept in his book *The Ecological Approach to Visual perception*¹⁷. An *affordance* is a property or set of properties of an object, which provides guidance on how to interact with that object or one of its features. The term became diffuse in *design* thanks to Don Norman and his famous *The Design of Everyday Things* in 1988.

2.4.5. Sound

Sound is often only a small part in an *interaction design* process but can be very important, especially for warnings and environmental devices. Sound consists of three main components, each of which can be adjusted by a *designer*:

- **pitch**, how high a sound is in frequency;
- **volume**, how loud a sound is in intensity;
- **quality** of timbre or tone, what kind of sound it is.

Sound is underused, but in *interaction design* it can produce an important difference in a product. Just think of the *iPod* knob, Steve

¹⁷ J. J. GIBSON, *The Ecological Approach to Visual perception*, Boston, Houghton Mifflin, 1979.

Jobs insisted quite affintil he produced an audible *click* even with the cuffie on.

2.5. The Laws of Interaction Design

All these previously analysed elements must be assembled by an *Interaction Designer* according to certain principles or laws. Considering that *Interaction Design* is a relatively new field, *Interaction Designers* are recently discovering many of the basic principles of the work they do. Nevertheless, there are already many laws that *Interaction Designers* have used successfully.

2.5.1 Moore's Law

Moore, co-founder of the giant *Intel*, predicted that every two years the number of *transistors* on circuits would double. And that is what is happening and is happening. Suffice it to say that there is more computing power in a PC today than in the entire control centre of NASA in 1969, when they sent the first man to the moon. *Designers* can therefore conceive of even smaller and faster devices than could have been imagined a decade ago.

2.5.2. Fitts' law

S vilupplied¹⁸ in 1954 by psychologist Paul M. Fitts, Fitts' law states that the time to reach a target (an area or a button for example) in a pointing action, called a task, depends on the distance of the object to be reached and the size of that object. Trivially, the larger and closer the object, the faster the task.

By task, we mean a continuous movement starting from a certain position and ending above the target to be reached. Obviously, to say that the larger and closer an object is, the faster it will be positioned over it does not seem like much of a discovery at first glance. Fitts' law, however, defines in terms

¹⁸ P. M. FITTS, *The information capacity of the human motor system in controlling the amplitude of movement* in *Journal of Experimental Psychology*, 'Vol. 47, No. 6', Columbus, The Ohio State University 1954.

numerical, quantitative, the acquisition time, given the distance and size of the target and known some variables, according to the following formula:

$$MT = a + b \cdot \log_2 \left(\frac{d}{s} + 1 \right)$$

where:

- MT = *movement* time to a target;
- d = distance between the pointing device¹⁹ (e.g. the pointer on the screen) and the object;
- s = size, i.e. the size of the object (measured on the axis of movement).

In the original formula, the values of a and b were: a = 0.230 s; b = 0.166 s, but they vary depending on the situation and can be derived experimentally. Using this formula, a pointer must reach a target of size s via a linear path of the resulting length. Fitts' Law is therefore a formula that can predict the aiming time of an object quite accurately and its validity has been repeatedly confirmed empirically.

The consequences for the design of graphical user interfaces are many. The most important, probably, is that the quickest point to reach is, of course, where the pointer already is. This is obvious, because there is no movement to be made, neither fast nor slow. This property is implemented in the context menu, the one activated by clicking the right mouse button, in the use of a different *gesture* in touch screen devices or in the use of several fingers in contexts where there is the possibility of using *multitouch*²⁰. Apart from where the mouse cursor is located, Fitts' law also determines which other points on the screen are quickest to reach.

¹⁹ When Fitts' law was conceived, no thought was given to devices with touch displays, but this approach is also applicable to this outfit. In this case, the pointing device is represented by the fingertips used to effect the action and the distance, which is the line joining the pointing device and the target, is to be calculated in physical space.

²⁰ A *multitouch* touch screen is differentiated from its predecessors in that it is sensitive to touch at several different points on the surface simultaneously. This awareness of a plurality of points is often used to implement advanced functionality using two or more fingers.

Quick points

As one can easily imagine, the fastest points do not affectly depend on where the cursor is located. They are in fact very fast points that can be reached from any point. They are in fact the four corners of the screen if we are in a context where the pointer is the *mouse* or the edges of the *display* in a context where the *input is* touch.

The four corners

For the four corners, the reason is very simple, the movement can be very fast (one can 'throw' the *mouse* towards the corner), without having to resort to fine adjustments, since the corner does not allow the *mouse* to go further. In this way, it is as if the 'corner' object had infinite dimension, since we can imagine it as an object that extends at will beyond the limits of the screen. A practical application of this concept can be found in the macOS operating system where, since its introduction in the early 2000s, it has been possible to assign functions to the four corners of the screen.

It is for this reason that the Macintosh's graphical user interface, from its first Mac OS in 1984 to today, has menu bars bordering the edge of the screen. A feature that makes it very easy to reach the menu items.

A mistake made by all versions of Windows, and only partly corrected with the X P version, is that it distances the items placed on the task bar at the bottom a few *pixels* from the edge of the screen. Also spaced out, again by a few *pixels*, is the start button, which could instead benefit from the perfectly 'angled' position.

It should be specified that the fact that objects are only a few *pixels* away from the edge does not make them 'just a little' less quick to reach. In fact, it makes it necessary to control fine movements (which are the ones that waste time) and therefore objects, although close to the edge, are effected objects like all others: either they are placed exactly on the edge, or they will not benefit from Fitts' law in comparison with other objects of the same size.

The edges of the display

After the four corners, obviously the quickest points to reach are the edges of the display, even if only in one direction. The assumption of infinite size also applies to them. The edges are of utmost importance in *mobile devices* with *touch* displays, but here the position with which the device is held must also be taken into consideration.

An interesting example can be found by analysing how Apple redesigned the device's unlocking system after abandoning the physical button. iPhones since their introduction in 2007 have had a central physical button that was used for unlocking the device's screen and for calling up the Home screen. The entire user experience was conveyed through this button. Obviously, the abandonment of this element on a large part of the range, starting with the model made for the tenth anniversary (iPhone X), will have been the subject of much discussion and careful study. The physical button has been replaced by a *swipe gesture* executed on the bottom edge of the *display* and it is therefore clear that the *Interaction Designer* who designed it took into account the fundamentals of Fitts' law, and that of physical space, i.e. the position commonly used to hold the smartphone.

Considerations on web interfaces

Obviously, the way the web is, no page can benefit from placing buttons or links adjacent to the edge of the screen, simply because we are bound to the *browser* window, which floats on the screen without a fixed position, and even when used in full-screen mode

have a margin of a few *pixels*²¹ which makes the attempt to make considerations on the use of corner or edge positions. However, a statistical assumption that can be made is that the *mouse* pointer gravitates on average more often near the scroll bar, i.e. to the right of the *browser* window.

²¹ Historically, the most common *browsers* such as *Internet Explorer*, *Firefox*, and *Opera* have long presented the contents of web pages framed by a border of a few *pixels*, but in recent years the trend, initiated by the *Safari* browser, has been to eliminate this border and provide totally *borderless* windows.

Of course, the advantages are few and do not merit very strict *design* constraints, but it is still a consideration aimed at ease of use. Nowadays, with the wide diffusion of mice with *scrolling* functionality integrating ²², the pointer is less likely to be relegated to the right-hand side of the screen, and the advantages of this positioning will also slowly diminish. Furthermore, once the first screen tends to be longer and populated with menus, the advantage disappears.

The buffer zones

Fitts' law takes the acquisition time into account, but not the error rate. In theory, areas that make maximum use of the law, such as the context menu, corners or sides have very low or zero error rates. Sometimes, necessity forces many icons and buttons into a small space, reducing their size and thus increasing the error rate.

If icons that are too small are adjacent, then an error may cause the wrong button to be clicked, triggering an unwanted action. To reduce this risk, designers sometimes use to insert a small (a few pixels are sufficient) non-clickable space between icon and icon, called the *buffer* area. The *buffer* area does not reduce the error: it ensures that the error does not produce undesirable consequences. This obviously goes against Fitts' law (in fact, it serves to keep people from clicking).

The reason is obvious: given a certain available space and a certain number of objects (buttons, icons), the insertion of buffer zones reduces the size of the objects. Buffer zones should therefore be inserted with a certain amount of caution, only where the targets are small and the risk of error may result in undesired actions. In any case, they should not be larger than a few *pixels*.

Wherever possible, the error rate is reduced by simply making the individual clickable zones larger, so that a user is more unlikely to click on the edge but rather clicks in the middle.

Fitts' Law, especially for *mobile* applications, should also make us remember that conditions and variations for special cases (e.g. for people with motor disorders) should be tested. People with disabilities do not all have the same disabilities and do not even use

²² An example is the classic wheel or the more modern *touch* surfaces integrated on the back of the mouse.

all the same pointing devices. In these cases, Fitts' law applies as long as the movement is continuous and there is a linear correspondence between the physical movement of the disabled person and the movement of the virtual pointer. If, due to effect of a lack of movement control, or due to the use of pulsating cursor systems, or other discrete pointing mechanisms, Fitts' Law does not have to be taken into account, but it has to be verified on a case-by-case basis what the problems are for that category of disabled person.

2.5.3.Hick's Law

Hick's law states that the time it takes users to make decisions is determined by the number of possible choices they have. If there are n equiprobable alternatives, the time it takes to choose one is given by the formula:

$$time = a + b \cdot \log_2 (n + 1)$$

This can be explained by the fact that, at the time of a choice, instead of considering each option in the set one at a time, we subdivide the set of options into categories, progressively discarding some of them (about half at each step). Therefore, all things being equal (constants a and b), as the number of options increases, the reaction time also increases.

This law is not always applicable, in fact in the case of a disordered list of options it is difficult to perform the mental decomposition into categories that Hick's law presupposes; the choice time then becomes linear and the formula loses its meaning. Conversely, if a list of options is presented according to a logical (e.g. alphabetical) criterion, it is possible to use a decomposition criterion for the choices; time in this case is in a non-linear relationship with the number of alternatives and the law is relevant.

A controversial consequence of this law is that for products it is better to give users several choices simultaneously instead of organising the choices into hierarchical groups, as in drop-down menus.

If followed to the extreme, this approach would create questionable *design* solutions, imagine if a site rich in content and options such as *eBay* presented all *links* on the main page or a *smartphone* displayed all functionality on one screen ²³. Hick's Law also states that the time required to make a decision is influenced by two factors, familiarity with the choices, given for example by repeated use, and the format of the choices. The principles of Hick's Law seem to contradict Miller's magic rule number 7.

2.5.4. The law of the magic number 7

George Miller, in 1956, determined that the human mind is most capable of remembering information in pieces of seven elements.

It would seem that man has difficulties to hold more than that amount of information in his short-term memory at any given time. Many designers have taken the number seven to the extreme, making sure that there are no more than seven items on a screen at any given time.

Designers must take care not to create products that cause *cognitive overload*, because by ignoring the law of the magic number 7, they force users to remember unfamiliar elements found in different screens or pages.

2.5.5. Tesler's law or conservation of complexity

Larry Tesler, one of the pioneers of *interaction design*, coined this law that states that a certain amount of complexity is inherent in any process. There is a point beyond which you cannot further simplify a process; you can only support the inherent complexity from one side to the other.

If, for example, the recipient's or sender's address is *missing* when sending an e-mail, the *e-mail* cannot be sent, full stop. It is a

²³ Whether by choice or compulsion, this approach was, at least at an early stage, used by the first *iPhone 2G*. This model released only in the United States, with its first OS release, did not have the possibility of adding *apps* to the system ones and therefore presented all functionalities on a single screen.

necessary complexity. Every time we send an e-mail, we do not have to enter our address each time, the same for the recipient's; the software stores recent addresses, so we do not have to remember them.

Complexity has not gone away, but some of it has instead moved into software. Tesler's law should be remembered by every *interaction designer* for two reasons:

1. one must realise that all processes have elements that cannot be simplified;
2. one has to look for reasonable places to move this complexity in the products created.

CHAPTER 3: USER-CENTRED DESIGN (UCD)

UCD, or *User-Centred Design*²⁴, is a way to design and build websites or applications taking into account the user's point of view and needs, which is based on the iteration of different analysis or observation, design and verification tools.

3.1 Introduction

In the previous chapters we have defined the disciplinary field of reference and the specific skills that a *UX designer* must possess in order to be able to exercise his profession to the best of his ability; in this chapter we will look in more detail at what activities a *User Experience* project is made up of and, once the reference method has been framed, the main methods employed in the various phases of design and the support tools for carrying out the various activities.

3.2. Description

User-centred design is an iterative process that focuses on understanding users and their context at all stages of design and development. As we have seen in previous chapters, UCD is the paradigm of reference for IxD and *UX design*. Using a *user-centred* methodology means not only designing for the user, but also co-designing with the user. In fact, the method envisaged by the UCD approach foresees an active involvement of users in all design phases, according to a perspective that defines the *UX designer* as a vehicle and interpreter of their needs and preferences. Another qualifying characteristic of UCD is iterativity: the design process of a technological artefact does not proceed in a straight line from the *brief*

²⁴ Commonly abbreviated to UDC.

to implementation, but envisages several cycles of evaluation (and possibly *user testing*), 'correction' and design: a process of continuous research, by trial and error, proposing solutions that are gradually improved, in a path of progressive approach to the *optimum*. *This is* another element that confirms the centrality of the user and makes the work of the UX less self-referential (and therefore more complex); in fact, the *designer* 'cannot afford' to conceive an idea and realise it according to his inspiration and taste, but must always confront himself with his addressee, collect his preferences, comments, suggestions and modify it accordingly.

3.2.1. An innovative working method

The UCD is thus clearly distinguished from the classic 'waterfall' model typical of software engineering; the conceptualisation proposed by Garrett ²⁵ with regard to *website* development is in fact efficacious for any digital artefact and completes the picture of the process outlined above.

Specifically, Garrett identifies five planes that conceptually represent the 'layers' of a product:

1. the **strategy**: the overall objective of the system to be designed, which can be defined by understanding who the target audience is and what needs (both user and business) are to be satisfied;
2. the **product**: you will build the purpose of the product i.e. its specific functionalities, the content it has to convey, in technical terms this means defining a list of requirements;
3. the **structure**: **this** represents a fundamental junction in the process, being the concept on which the project is based, which takes the form of an information architecture that defines the mutual relations between the various functions and the information conveyed by the system;
4. the **skeleton**: in English *wireframe*, *it* is what gives a structure its shape. It concerns the *design of the* interaction in the strict sense, i.e. it defines the

²⁵ GARRETT J. J., *The elements of User Experience: User Centered Design for the web and beyond*, Pearson Education, 2010.

navigation model of the artefact, the *user flow*, in order to translate the underlying architecture in a usable manner;

5. finally, the **surface: the** last layer, the so-called *look & feel* of the interface, the visible part of the interface, which will be directly manipulated by the end user.

Each of these plans can easily be traced back to the phases and specific activities envisaged by the UCD method, and the model is therefore useful to better understand how the design of a digital artefact is a complex process of progressive construction of the final result, in which each step is important and forms a basis for the next.

The soundness of the lower layers, i.e. the accuracy and expertise with which the activities concerning them have been carried out, affects that of the overlapping states, so a check on the former leads to better final results. In short, the iterative model of UCD that we are going to describe is clarified and completed by the concept of layering.

3.3. The PACT approach

The reference system for any designer of interactive artefacts consists of four fundamental elements, theorised in the PACT working *framework* ²⁶, which must therefore be known, analysed, kept in mind and involved in the various steps of the design itself:

- **people**, the users for whom the product is intended, with their specific characteristics, tastes, needs and peculiarities;
- **activities**, which through the product should be performed, facilitated, made efficient and enjoyable;
- **contexts** in which people move and operate to perform the activities in question;
- available **technologies** capable of supporting the activities for the selected users, in the selected contexts.

²⁶ BENYON D., *Designing Interaction. Methods and techniques for interactive media design*, Pearson, 2012.

The PACT framework makes clear the importance of the transversality of the competences of a UX *designer* and constitutes a benchmark for all methods and techniques used in the various stages of the UCD process.

In the following, with the description of the main among these methods, it will become even clearer how the four elements mentioned above are present and combine in a UX Design project, to the extent that they are the very stuff of it.

3.4. The classical UCD approach

In general, the classical UCD approach involves four distinct phases. First, as *designers* working as a team, one tries to understand the context in which users may use a system. Then, user requirements are identified and specified. This is followed by a design phase, in which the design team develops solutions. The team then proceeds to an evaluation phase in which the results of the evaluation are assessed against the context and user requirements, to check the performance of a design. More specifically, it is checked how close it is to a level that corresponds to the users' specific context and meets all their relevant requirements. From there, the team performs further iterations of these four steps and continues until the evaluation results are satisfactory.

3.4.1. Analyses the context

The first step in a digital project is to collect and analyse information in order to define a general strategy to be followed, based on the needs of *target* users on the one hand and *business* objectives on the other. It is indeed

It is from this that the so-called functional specifications of the digital system will be defined.

The analysis phase can be schematically divided into two large groups of activities, defined on the basis of the object of study: analysis of users on the one hand and analysis of contexts, activities, technologies on the other.

User Research

The first group of activities, called *User Research*, consists of a series of methods borrowed from social research and readapted to the needs of speed and flexibility of design, so much so as to be defined as 'rapid ethnography' tools: that is, practices such as questionnaires, interviews, direct observation. Below we will briefly look at those that are most frequently employed.

Quantitative survey

Questionnaires or *surveys*, a quantitative survey tool, make it possible to reach relatively large samples of users, collecting data on preferences, needs, personal characteristics, consumption habits and technology use. In short, they are a valuable channel for obtaining statistically valid data that will allow users to be characterised by identifying typical patterns of behaviour, preferences and potentially subdividing them into subgroups.

A questionnaire typically contains a series of multiple-choice questions aimed at collecting comparable data from different users. The questions proceed from the general to the particular, focusing increasingly on what the researcher is interested in knowing about the users.

Since it is not advisable to make too onerous demands on the user, the time required to complete a questionnaire should never exceed 15-20 minutes. Therefore, it will be essential to include a limited number of questions to be asked focusing very specifically on what one wants to know, studying the answer options to offire so that they are as informative as possible during the analysis phase.

Questions usually involve a single answer among several options (*radio button, drop-down list*), several answers in a list of possibilities (*check box*), placement on a scale (numerical, e.g. 1-10, or a 5- or 7-point Likert scale ²⁷) and finally open questions. The latter are usually included to collect suggestions and have great informative potential. Clearly, the analysis effort for these types of answers can also be very onerous in relation to the size of the sample.

The main difficulties in the formulation of a questionnaire lie in selecting the 'right' questions to ask (all and only those necessary) and formulating them in a clear, unintelligible, non-biased manner so as not to bias the answers.

Tools such as *Google Forms, Survey Monkey* (and many others) are easy to use and low cost (they have free basic versions and paid versions that are not very expensive in any case) and are therefore an excellent way to easily differ quantitative surveys via *email, social networks, websites*.

Qualitative survey

If quantitative survey techniques allow the collection of statistical data, probing in particular the behaviour of the intended users, qualitative survey has the merit of focusing on aspects more related to their opinions, preferences, the nuances of their way of thinking and approaching the product/service.

A good compromise between the level of user involvement and the cost (in terms of time as well as expense) to conduct the research is represented by semi-structured interviews. These combine the existence of a scheme, a predefined outline of questions, with a flexibility of management

²⁷ The Likert scale is a psychometric technique for measuring attitude invented by the psychologist *Rensis Likert*. This technique is mainly distinguished by the possibility of applying item analysis methods based on the statistical properties of interval or ratio scales. *Likert's* method, which is quicker and simpler than *Thurstone's* earlier scales, was, and still is, adopted in numerous areas of applied research. This technique mainly consists of developing a certain number of affirmations, called *items*, which express a positive and negative attitude towards a specific object. The sum of these judgements will tend to delineate the subject's attitude towards the object in a reasonably precise manner. For each item, a scale of agreement or disagreement is presented, generally with 5 or 7 modes.

of the conversation itself, which allows the interviewee to freely address the topics in the order he or she prefers.

The structure serves to orient the interview in such a way that it remains focused on the topic and is useful in acquiring all the information established as necessary; the fruitfulness of the interview is therefore affdependent on the interviewer's management skills, i.e. his ability to put the subject at ease and give him freedom to express himself, without losing *focus*.

An interview lasts on average one hour and includes a so-called *warm-up* phase, in which one 'gets to know' the interviewee and

try to put him at ease; then the questions, always open ²⁸ and colloquialisms converge on the process and activities under investigation, soliciting the user's personal point of view.

The collection of stories is a frequently used expedient during interviews, aimed at sharing success stories and critical experiences concerning the activity or system studied. The purpose of the stories is to describe in narrative form and in rich detail the good practices or difficulties encountered during the activity; through them it is possible to confirm personal beliefs and attitudes, needs and values that characterise the activities.

Another instrument of qualitative investigation is field observation. This is a research technique that originates in the so-called *field studies*, typical of the social sciences and anthropology, and allows for an invaluable amount and quality of data to be obtained as people are contacted in their natural environment. Difficilly, such rich contextual information can be obtained with other methods. This results in a large amount of data to be analysed and not easy to interpret, which makes this method costly in terms of the resources that have to be deployed.

In practice, these are actual observation sessions of the subjects while they perform the activities under investigation in their usual context and using tools that are familiar to them; the experimenter's work is guided by an observation grid that helps him/her focus on important details and note down comparable elements between the various subjects observed.

²⁸ i.e. questions involving an argumentative and discursive answer, usually these questions begin with an adverb e.g. "*How... ?*" and do not include the possibility of answering with a "*yes*" or "*no*".

The researcher may or may not participate in the interaction and in some cases the user may be asked to perform tasks, in a manner similar to *user tests* (which we will describe later). In the analysis, care must be taken to use descriptive and not evaluative language.

3.4.2. Specify requirements

Requirements analysis supports design in identifying which functional characteristics the product should have, taking into account two types of requirements: those coming from the users (*user needs*) and those coming from the customer (*business requirements*). The aim is to identify a list of functionalities that the system will have to support through activities, established in production and industrial engineering, such as *benchmarks*, *task analysis*, *personas* and *scenarios*.

Benchmark

Benchmarking, or competitive analysis, is one of the most diffuseful methods of analysis in the various fields of product design and conception. It consists of studying the players in a particular market sector to see which products are present, *best practices* to imitate and mistakes to avoid. The activity may be carried out at different levels of detail on the characteristics of the digital system/service in question, and the related *report* may result in a schematic document listing the individual characteristics, or in a more detailed one showing *screenshots* of the various elements in the various systems examined.

Task Analysis

Task analysis is a useful method for gaining a thorough understanding of the process of the activities in which the user is involved in order to achieve his or her goals; it is based on the analytical examination of all the *steps* necessary for the user to complete a certain task and models the activity by dividing it into:

- main objective;
- sub-objectives;

- necessary actions.

It is used to identify areas of criticality with reference to both the characteristics of the users and how the product will be used, the requirements for the new system to be designed and the production technologies that can be used. It also makes it possible to identify the risks to which a user is subject during an action, to predict which errors a user will be most likely to make and to define the skills and competencies required of users to perform tasks. The activity involves the study and subsequent detailed schematisation of the individual activities that make up the action flows and the result may be a textual list or table of activities broken down into sub-tasks or a flow chart.

Personas

Users are not an amorphous mass, but a collection of people with their own characteristics and peculiarities, technology use habits, knowledge, preferences, which can be segmented into meaningful categories precisely on the basis of these characteristics. The instrument of *personas* (an Englishism that takes up the Latin word *persona*) serves precisely this purpose: they are invented personas that embody the needs and characteristics of an entire group of real users. The *persona* is in other words an archetype (ideal type) that describes a certain category of users and represents a useful reference for the UX *designer* to:

- establish *user needs* and specify product requirements;
- facilitate the sharing of *design* ideas in the team.

Users can be segmented according to many criteria or even combinations of these, such as:

- demographic factors (age, gender, education level, income, marital status);
- psychographic factors (relating to perceptions and attitudes that the users may have towards the products);
- character elements (enthusiasts *vs.* sceptics);
- technological *expertise* (experts *vs.* novices);

- domain expertise (how experienced are users in that particular application domain?);
- frequency of use (regular *vs.* occasional);
- cultural differences etc.

Characters can be constructed from data obtained in the *User Research* phase or thanks to collaborative *design activities* in which project *stakeholders* are involved (see below for an explanation of co-design workshop activities); finally, we speak of "*proto-personas*" in cases in which the archetypes are elaborated from the *designer's* knowledge, both domain and general, referring to acquaintances, reasoning by opposites or imagining possible scenarios. The collected characteristics are synthesised through several personas that reflect them comprehensively. The strength of this tool lies in the fact that personas are more easily remembered than simple data, so designing with someone in mind helps the *designer* to keep their needs more strongly in mind. However, not all *personas* (and the categories of users they represent) carry the same weight in defining the objectives of a digital project, so it is important to distinguish between:

- *primary personas*, the primary *target audience*;
- *secondary personas*, other potential *targets*;
- *negative personas*, the *target* group we would like to exclude.

Scenarios

People live user experiences and tell them in the form of stories; the stories of several persons in the same user group may also have many points of contact, share not only the same actions and tools, but also the same contexts of use and even the same problems. In short, from the narratives of experiences and anecdotes collected during the *User Research* phase, the UX can abstract scenarios, i.e. the stories that tell of people (our *personas*) performing activities in certain contexts, using particular technologies, having precise needs and preferences. Just like *personas*, scenarios are very useful tools because they represent real or at least

realistic for *design*, they delimit the so-called 'design space' and provide precise descriptions of potential use situations. They are used both in the conception and design phase, because they provide a starting point for prototyping, and in the various evaluation cycles, because concrete use cases can be derived from them, to be tested in user tests.

3.4.3. Design

The analysis phase is useful to clarify the project brief and define the requirements, identifying specific users to be taken as reference and usage situations to be supported in the project:

- **functional requirements**, what the system must do (list of functionalities);
- **non-functional requirements**, what features it must have (aesthetics, usability, performance, etc.).

On this basis, it is then possible to hypothesise one or more *design* solutions at an abstract level for the time being, bringing together all the elements, i.e. people, actions, contexts, technologies.

Concept

The concept *of* a project is the idea, the rationale that is combined into a coherent and logical whole:

- a **conceptual model** of the system, defined by the basic principles, the keywords on which it is based (also called *pillars*) and in some cases a reference metaphor;
- a **structure**, i.e. the information architecture of the system (which will be described later in this chapter);
- **layout specifications**, which will be explored in detail later, concerning basic screens.

In essence, then, the *concept* defines the characteristics of the system in terms of usability, performance, aesthetics, efficiency, and security, making a synthesis and then abstraction operation on the data collected during the analysis

phase.

Brainstorming among the members of a UX team (or in *workshop* sessions with users) helps to formalise requirements and explore *design* solutions, bearing in mind the constraints that each project imposes (time, financial, technological, etc.), but exploring all available space by defining a divergent phase, and then converging on the most robust solutions by defining a convergent phase.

Information Architecture

Information architecture is at the heart of any *Interaction Design* project. It represents the structure of the information space in which people move to perform their tasks and find the information they need. In other words, it defines the hierarchical and logical relationships between the various portions of information contained in the system, taking into account the processes and thus defining the real degree of usability and usability of a system for the end user.

Building a solid AI is a prerequisite for a project that wants to be sustainable, functional, and able to truly support the paths and flows of activity that the user will have to travel.

Co-design workshops

One method that allows a practical result and thus imprinting clear guidelines on the subsequent work phases, involving all influential actors in a project (internal the client and external, such as end users) is the *co-design workshop*.

Subjects with different professionalism, skills, knowledge and operational levels are put in a position to collaborate and discuss operational issues related to the activities, technologies and contexts of use concerning the product to be designed. The sessions, lasting a few hours, involve careful planning and a major management effort on the part of the UX, which proposes to the subjects activities designed *ad hoc* in relation to the operational purpose of the *workshop*; some typical activities are *card sorting* exercises, the

brainstorming, the construction of maps such as the *experience map*²⁹ or the generation of scenarios and *personas*.

The presence of all actors at the same working table allows all competences to be aligned towards the same objective in a short time, through the shared generation of a common proposition. The creative and participative value of the *workshop* allows the different actors to identify with the proposed solution. *Co-design workshops* are useful both in the *concept* and design phase, and at the beginning, as an analysis tool.

Prototyping

The *concept* of a project necessarily includes rough indications of the *layout*, which set the navigation model of the system. For the new proposal to take shape, and be intelligible to potential users, it is then necessary to develop prototypes that can be shown and shared.

The most immediate and least structured level of prototyping is the *sketch*: a quick, inexpensive but efficacious 'pencil' drawing to visualise *design* solutions and make it easy to share within the *design team*, stimulating the development of possible alternative solutions. *Sketches* are in fact the starting point of any UX project and are crucial in highlighting any interaction issues.

If *sketches* are indispensable in defining a *concept*, in the next phase, that of detailed *design*, the established guidelines will necessarily have to be declined and specified in navigation paths that illustrate how the main *tasks* will be supported by the new product.

Wireframes are drawings of the *layout* of system pages that can have different levels of detail, from schematic (*low-fi wireframe*) to high-fidelity (*hi-fi wireframe*) versions. The main *wireframing tools*

²⁹ In this regard, I refer to the excellent ebook distributed free of charge: M. C. LAVAZZA, *Le User Experience Map: cosa sono, a cosa servono, come farle*, Bento book, 2014.

SKETCH³⁰, BALSAMIQ WIREFRAMES³¹, AXURE³², OMNIGRAFFLE³³ and also allow the generation of *html* prototypes simulating the behaviour of the various elements on the page. Others, such as INVISION³⁴ or MARVEL³⁵ generate working prototypes from graphic drawings of the pages or interfaces already at the level of the so-called *front-end* at a level of detail very close to the final one.

3.4.4. Currency

The defining characteristic of UCD is iterativity, i.e. the repetition of cycles of evaluation and redesign of *design* solutions towards an optimal final product. When is it useful to evaluate? It is useful to evaluate all the time. One evaluates the concept, one evaluates prototypes at different levels of definition. One continues to evaluate even after the release of a product.

Of the various existing evaluation methods, two are the most frequently used:

Evaluation Euristic a36

³⁰ Sketch by Bohemian Coding is a vector graphics creation software for macOS, was first released on 7 September 2010 and won an Apple Design Award in 2012, (www.sketch.com) [last accessed: 19.04.2020].

³¹ Balsamic Wireframes by Balsamiq Studios LLC, is a software for creating *wireframes*, was invented by a former Adobe employee, PELDI GUILIZZONI, in 2008, (balsamiq.com) [last accessed: 19.04.2020].

³² Axure RP from Axure Software Solutions, is a tool used to make *wireframes* and rapid prototypes of *software* interfaces, applications and *websites*, (www.axure.com) [last accessed: 19.04.2020].

³³ OmniGraffle by The Omni Group, is a digital diagram and illustration application for macOS and iOS, (www.omnigroup.com) [last accessed: 19.04.2020].

³⁴ InVision by InVisionApp Inc., is a software that helps in the design of *websites* and *mobile apps*, focusing on optimising the collaborative and creative process, allowing, among other things, to effect *testing* as well, (www.invisionapp.com) [last accessed: 19.04.2020].

³⁵ Marvel from Marvel Prototyping Ltd. is a *rapid prototyping* software that allows even those with zero previous experience to create *lo-fi* prototypes. It is widely used as a Sketch *plugin* and the *mobile companion app* that allows the created prototype to be quickly viewed on *mobile* devices is very popular, (www.invisionapp.com) [last accessed 19.04.2020].

³⁶ In Greek, *eurisko*, '*eurish'*, means 'I discover, I find'.

It is an inspection activity, i.e. not an empirical one, which serves to detect the fidelity and adherence of the interface to shared usability guidelines, conducted by *user interface* experts who explore the system to detect whether the principles of good design are correctly applied and possibly identify critical areas to be worked on.

The guidelines referred to for evaluations are the usability heuristics of Jakob Nielsen ³⁷, which identify the fundamental and inviolable principles of correct UX design. Normally, the evaluation is carried out in parallel by at least two (preferably three) usability experts, who perform multiple navigations of the system, preferably performing predefined *tasks*, and identify any violations, also assigning a severity score to them, in order to identify priorities for action. The evaluations gathered in this way are then compared and integrated with each other, resulting in a single classification of problems and leading to (more or less precise) indications for redesign.

The main advantages of heuristic evaluation clearly lie in its cost-effectiveness, speed and ease of execution; its potential limitation is determined by the level of experience and expertise of the individual evaluators. It remains one of the preferred methods for evaluation, particularly of products to be redesigned.

User test

It is an empirical method of evaluation based on the involvement of end-users corresponding to the target *audience*; they are asked to perform certain meaningful tasks in order to identify possible criticalities of the interface.

This activity can be carried out at any time during product development: in the design phase (on prototypes) or after release, on the working product (this is the case of tests oriented towards the *redesign* of a system). At whatever point in time it is carried out, it is very useful in identifying problems that users encounter in using the tool and that may have escaped expert evaluation. This allows correct *design* decisions to be made (from the

³⁷ J. NIELSEN, *10 Usability Heuristics for User Interface Design*, (www.nngroup.com 24 April 1994) [last accessed: 07.04.2020].

user's point of view) and to implement adjustments to the design that will avoid costly modifications after release (or, worse, a bad user experience).

Good preparation of the *user test* is crucial to ensure its performance in terms of the indications collected; it is therefore important:

- **define its objectives:** these can be generic or specific (testing the intuitiveness of the whole system or instead specific functions);
- **identify the sample** of subjects: how many users, with which characteristics (age, *expertise*...);
- **defining tasks:** drawing up a test protocol;
- deciding how to **measure** usability: quantitative and/or qualitative.

Selected subjects are given an introductory explanation that also serves to put them at ease, making it clear that the object of the test is the system and not their *performance*, and are asked to verbalise their thoughts as they are trying to complete the various tasks. In fact, the cognitive *think loud* technique allows the user's mental model to emerge when faced with the performance of a task.

Tests are normally recorded in audio and video, using *tools* that also allow *screen recording* (e.g. *FlashBack*, *usertesting.com*, *Loop 1* or, where present, the system screen recorder), which is useful for reviewing and analysing the material collected.

The final outcome of the tests are precise indications of *redesign*, but also general directions to follow in order to continue the project.

Certainly, organising and conducting user tests are time-consuming and resource-intensive activities, but it is also true that it is not

necessary to test large numbers of users: according to Nielsen ³⁸ in fact, testing as few as 5 users can detect 85% of a product's usability problems. It must be said

that, even in the absence of sophisticated instrumentation or large samples of users, if the UX *team* is short of resources or in the presence of unsophisticated prototypes, doing *user testing* is still useful and always brings new and non-trivial knowledge to *designers*. It is possible to carry out

³⁸ J. NIELSEN, *Why You Only Need to Test with 5 Users*, (www.nngroup.com 18 March 2000) [last accessed: 07.04.2020].

so-called '*discount*' tests, using *paper & pencil* prototypes and traditional video recording tools. However they are done, testing is useful and testing a few users is still better than testing none, because even the most experienced UX cannot have insights into all the important aspects for a user in a user experience.

3.4.5. The 'conclusion' of the process

Relevant data was collected and processed, a *design* concept was realised, developed in detail through evaluation and redesign cycles, leading to an optimal solution: solid, efficabile, intuitive.

The work of the UX is therefore finished, one might say, but no. Because the UX *concept* of a system will have to be affianched by a graphic *concept*, a visual mood that will have to support it and actually define the *look & feel* characteristics of the final interface, the one that the user will manipulate. Therefore, it is part of the UX's duties to supervise and affianchor the work of the graphic designers, who will have to integrate and complete *wireframes*, prototypes and of course the final product.

On the other hand, the work of implementing the system will also have to be followed by the UX, which will have the task of affianchoring the programmers, receiving from them any need to reconsider certain functionalities or behaviours and guiding them in the correct realisation of the system's requirements; this in order to obtain a final *output* that reflects the project resulting from all the activities previously carried out.

This makes it even clearer how transversal the composition of a UX *team* is and what the most complex skill required of a *user experience designer* is: the ability to mediate, to act as an interpreter and bridge between the needs, preferences, and tastes of users and one's own expertise, opinions, and previous experience; between creativity and the tendency to innovate and the need to keep in touch with real contexts; between the creativity and personality of graphic designers and the need for minimalism and intuitiveness; between the limits and difficulties of development techniques and the indispensable need to go beyond these and overcome them.

All this in order to provide the user with the most rewarding user experience.

3.5. Application of UCD to Mobile

In modern work teams, particularly in the field of *mobile app* development, the *design* team is increasingly closer to the *developer* team, and this leads to making the iteration cycle of the UCD approach faster and faster, as it is often possible to implement the designed functionalities immediately, thus being able to evaluate them cyclically. Thus, by preserving a four-stage approach typical of UCD and reducing the first two parts of the classic process to a single analysis phase, we arrive at a schematisation of the four-stage process thus revised:

3.5.1. A five-step approach specifically for mobile

Introduction

Taking mobile into account is not an option but a priority for anyone who wants to make a new product and absolutely a necessity for those who need to upgrade a pre-existing product. Since the end of the last decade, there has been a steady percentage increase in Internet traffic produced by *mobile* devices compared to that produced by PCs and, in October 2010, there was a sor step³⁹. Today, estimates tell us that around 75 per cent of global internet traffico is produced by mobile devices and in particular by

³⁹ A. CREA, *Mobile surpasses desktop for traffico Internet*, (www.tomshw.it) [last accessed 27.03.2020].

smartphone. However, it is important to remember that having a mobile website or a native *mobile* application is not the key to success, but it does provide the right approach to user experience and a necessary first step that leads to success in this area. Taking a user-centred approach to *mobile* design can help you keep your intended results in mind rather than wasting time on projects without a specific *focus*.

By *mobile* where not specifically indicated we refer to both *mobile web* and *mobile app*. *Mobile web* is a description intended to distinguish internet access on a *tablet* or *smartphone* from a regular PC or *laptop*, by *mobile app* we mean a native application specifically designed for a portable device such as a *smartphone*, *tablet* or wearable devices such as *smartwatches*. As the world has adopted *smartphones* over the past decade, companies have realised the benefits of designing for the *mobile web*. However, too many companies start with the *end-point* "We need a *mobile app* or a *mobile website!*" in mind rather than considering why their users would want it. We must therefore focus on the benefits of providing a *mobile* experience:

- there is an opportunity to meet the specific needs of users at the right time and in the right place;
- can be accessed from *mobile* in places where the internet is not easily accessible from other devices;
- *mobile* development can be convenient and even cheaper than standard development;
- it is possible to reach a much broader user base (in correlation to internet traffic, we can assume that there are more *smartphone* owners than *desktop* and *laptop* owners);
- there is the possibility of reaching a much wider geographical area (in developing countries, *smartphones* are often the only way for a user to access the internet);
- the use of the potential of modern *displays* (such as advanced gestures thanks to the *multitouch*) and the large number of sensors available to developers makes it possible to create increasingly accessible solutions.

Application

We can identify five phases of the cycle (it is assumed that all development is cyclical with products going through several iterations in the course of life). Assess the situation as it is at the moment, in some cases it may be 'we don't have a mobile website' or perhaps 'our mobile app is not working as we hoped'. So you need to understand what users need. Once that is done, you prioritise the functionality for the *mobile* platform and then work on designing that functionality making sure you put 'mobile first' and finally review and refine the *design*.

1) Assessing the current situation

Mobile is an important thing because there are more *smartphone* and *tablet* users than PC and *desktop* users. But it cannot be assumed that users want to use the service via these platforms where it is not exclusively available via an exclusive channel (such as *Instagram*). In effects, recent research suggests that many users use *mobile* for a limited range of things (mainly dating, email, some *apps* and *social*) and that when users have an option they prefer to do more complex work from their *desktops*.

You have to think about whether a fully functional *mobile app* or *website* is really what you need, or is it possible that your users only need a small subset of functionality on the go and perhaps do most of their work on a *desktop*.

It is possible that your user base is less interested in a *mobile experience* and more interested in an enhanced experience with the products and platforms you already offer or vice versa that there is a need for a specific experience exclusively from *mobile*.

2) User Understanding

Before you affrush to prioritise any design or functionality, it is important to understand your users better and in a mobile context. You need to know things like:

- How do they prefer to access the Internet?
- How much time do they spend interacting with your site at the moment?
- How much time they spend online using an access point mobile?
 - What functionalities would be essential to provide a mobile experience?
 - What are they frustrated about in your offer at the moment and that they could be done better via a mobile device?
 - What devices do they use to access the mobile Web?

If you have more than one user, you will have to answer these questions on each user group. We also advise you to associate it with a 'top level' image. Find out and analyse trends in your industry and on *mobile*. You might find that, for some uses, *apps* are more popular than *mobile web* browsing and vice versa. Always keep the *focus* on what is important to users.

3) What offers your mobile experience?

So start prioritising what happens in your mobile experience. Your user research will show you what your users want, but you also need to consider what the company also wants from the process. You may need to review and modify components of the experience in order to manage conflicts between users and the company.

The user experience is essential but must always deliver tangible results, and by this is meant also the commercial and economic outcome. Compromise can be a key part of achieving the best possible result in the end. Don't forget that too much complexity at the beginning of the product life cycle can be a serious disadvantage, prioritising needs also means not being afraid to hold back ideas for future versions. An excellent *minimum viable product* (abbreviated MVP) can often be better than an overly complex product.

4) Specific considerations on mobile design

There will also be design considerations specific to mobile devices: such as the integration of the *mobile* offer with the actual offer, or the use of responsive *design* or adaptive *design*. Much of this comes down to context, for example the context in which the mobile device will be used. Whether users access the *mobile device* at home, at the supermarket, during their daily commute, at the coffee shop, etc. But also specifically whether they access it from their sofas, beds and many other places.

This means that one will have to consider how to reduce distractions and make it easy for the user to also concentrate on the activity at hand. Help is provided by the definition of access types, and the literature ⁴⁰, in this regard, defines three categories for *mobile* access:

1. **microtasking**: when users interact with their device for short but hectic periods of activity;
2. **local**: when the user wants to know what is happening around them;
3. **bored**: when the user has nothing better to do and seeks to be entertained or otherwise diverted.

Keeping these categories in mind can greatly simplify design according to user needs and focus on what makes mobile devices different from other access platforms.

5) *Review and refine*

Make sure to test sketches and prototypes produced in the early stages of iteration with users. Get *feedback* and iterate quickly. If you are designing for the web, do not forget to ensure compliance with the standards W3C41 and, in the case of *apps*, that they comply with the *design guidelines* suggested by the manufacturers of the operating systems ⁴².

⁴⁰ J. CLARK, *Tapworthy: Designing Great iPhone Apps*, O'Reilly Media, 2000.

⁴¹ 'The World Wide Web Consortium, also known as W3C, is a non-governmental organisation international organisation whose aim is to develop the full potential of the World Wide Web' s.v. 'World Wide Web Consortium', in AA. VV., *Wikipedia, the free encyclopaedia* (en.wikipedia.org) [last accessed 27.03.2020].

⁴² At the present time (2020), we are experiencing a substantial duopoly in the mobile sphere, represented by Apple's iOS platforms with the *Flat Design* paradigm and its '*Human Interface Guidelines*' and Google's Android, which largely uses the *Material Design* paradigm and its '*Material Design Guidelines*'.

At the end of this phase, one must then return to the beginning and iterate. This is why the user-centred design process for *mobile* devices, just like all user-centred design processes, is cyclical.

CHAPTER 4: INTERFACE DESIGN (*UI*)

UI, or *User Interface*, represents the actual graphical interface, that set of elements that allows interaction between the end user and the digital tool; in a website, for example, the button (or call to action) is the interface element that allows the user to perform a certain action (such as those listed above).

4.1. Introduction

Users are familiar with certain graphical elements, such as the button, and expect precise behaviour from them; the importance of fulfilling expectations by adopting predictable and consistent choices is therefore evident.

The interface is therefore the place where the choices of the IxD and UCD are realised, the tip of the *iceberg* of the complex work of the *UX Designer*. It represents how people can relate to a product and how that product should respond. In the case of *mobile* development, the expected *output* is the creation of visual interfaces.

The basis of all visual screen design is the layout: where and how features, controls and content are placed. It provides the structure in which these elements reside and the hierarchy, allowing users to understand what is most important or not. Layout is especially important for small screens, as space is at a premium.

In the western world, the eye generally moves from left to right and from top to bottom and designers must be aware of this and design accordingly. Grouping, subordinating, distancing, aligning creates the visual flow by emphasising certain functions over others, assimilating information by whispering to the user what is more important than something else, in what order one must proceed to complete a certain procedure and what other parallel possibilities there are in the same path.

To design the visual flow well, it is useful to keep in mind the laws of *Gestalt*. The lines, shapes, backgrounds and even counter spaces or rather the

particular relationships of all these elements suggest, according to the theory, movement, meaning, hierarchy, coherence and consequently the possibility of user-object interaction.

The same object has different characteristics when taken individually or placed within some other figure or grouping, and the same object, placed in two different totality, can take on different meanings. A well-constructed visual flow translates into psychological movement in the user's mind and leads him either straight to the target or off it. We will now review all the components required to produce efficient graphical interfaces.

4.2. General Notions

4.2.1. Grids

A grid helps the *designer* to organise information into a coherent screen and are one of the best systems you can use to guide people through the content you intend to create; you can rarely make wrong layout choices if you start with an organised grid system. To use them, one must have a good knowledge of lines and shapes and the basic rules of composition.

We start by dividing the screen into basic rational areas, which include *gutters*, the spaces separating rows and columns. Grids are guidelines that help the *designer* to organise the *layout* into a coherent scheme. They are not mandatory but strongly recommended, since, as Mark Boulton said back in 2005, *they "facilitate creativity by providing a framework for the work and answer some of the questions of future design"*⁴³. Furthermore, grids establish an order in the presentation of the visual flow and allow the user to easily identify where to look for the necessary information, buttons, commands, *widgets*, giving the *layout* a certain continuity.

The choice of grid depends on the *device we* are designing for and the type of product we are creating. For a photography *app*, the grid

⁴³ M. BOULTON, *Five simple steps to designing grid systems*, (markboulton.co.uk 4 July 2005) [last accessed 19.04.2020].

may be different from that for news, but the general trend is convergence and universality, whereby today's grids are fragmented into many cells, allowing for more and more flexibility in design.

The main differences are dictated by the size/proportions of device screens, related to their platform. Ratios are at the heart of any well-designed grid system, sometimes these ratios are rational, such as 1:2, 2:3 (the ratio of early *iPhones* or *iPads*), 4:3 (of early computer screens) or 16:10 (very diffuseful in modern *laptops*) others are irrational such as 1:1,414 (the ratio of A4) and new formats are on the horizon. It is important to study how to combine these ratios to create simple, balanced grids that in turn help create harmonious compositions. You can construct your own grid, *ad hoc* for a particular product, let yourself be helped by the *default grids* offered by the software commonly used in the world of digital graphics, or make use of the variety of free material available on the Net in different formats. The important thing is to take into account the continuous and rapid evolution of formats and trends. Designing the visual flow means providing clues as to where the user should look. The solutions designers propose must take into account the culture and situation in which future users live.

Grids are a product of the use of certain types of basis:

- **Guides:** the edge with which you choose to align the content.
- **Column:** element that creates a vertical division of content.
- **Line:** element that creates a horizontal division of content.
- **Margins:** the area surrounding the contents.
- **Gutter:** the margins between columns.
- **Hang-line:** a horizontal guide to align content to its lower part.
- **Baseline:** the horizontal guide for aligning content to its top.
- **Rithm:** proportion systems that can help define the dimensioning frequency and spacing of each of the above elements.

Although these components form the basic knowledge for a *designer*, usually covered in courses on core subjects such as typography and composition, they are a very difficult part of the work to master and require a high degree of experience to use wisely.

A good *designer* knows how to use a grid to guide users through content. An excellent *designer* knows when and where to break the grid to create something truly unique. A good example of this is Jon Moor's e44 off-centre alignment place, which can be a dangerous trend to follow if you don't have a purpose but if used wisely can lead to great results. In this regard it is worth pointing out an exclusive iOS *app* that has applied some principles of off-centre alignment, it is Bear, awarded the prestigious Apple Design Award in 2017, developed by the company Shiny Frog. Things that work for those who have experience and a strong motivation given by objective parameters but contextualised to their specific field of intervention, do not always work when trying to imitate it. So the advice for a young *designer* is to consolidate an understanding of the grid-based system for producing quality compositions and then be able to discern when and if it is necessary to break the mould to achieve a specific purpose.

4.2.2. Management of blanks

The *display*, which during normal daily use of an *app* is largely populated, may in some cases be empty, perhaps because the user has opened the application for the first time. We might find ourselves with an empty list of books, rather than songs or an empty customer address book.

Having a *blank slate* where there would normally be content is an opportunity for the *designer* to provide guidance and information on what the software can do. Leaving a blank screen would be a great missed opportunity to communicate something, so the *blank state* must be used to orient users. You can use blank states as an opportunity to provide advice, guidance, an overview of possible actions, or simply

⁴⁴ J. MOORE, *Tiny Trends #2: Off-Center Alignment*, (medium.com 10 January 2017) [last accessed 19.04.2020].

replace the blank status with a screen that allows users to enter missing information in a guided manner.

4.2.3. Gestalt

The work of so-called *gest* psychologists mainly concerns the study of the second stage of processing, i.e. how the visual process unconsciously tends to make order out of chaos, recognising objects from their separate parts and organising the visual elements into groups to form as unified and ordered an image as possible.

The results of this research have been crystallised in the so-called '*Gestalt* principles of perceptual organisation'. With particular reference to visual perceptions, the main rules of organisation of perceived data are:

- **Good figure:** the perceived structure is always the most simple.
- **Completeness (closure):** the brain is good at filling in the gaps to create everything.
- **Proximity:** elements are grouped according to of distances.
- **Similarity:** tendency to group similar elements together.
- **Good continuation:** all elements are perceived as belonging to a coherent and continuous whole.
- **Common fate:** if elements are moving, those with a consistent movement are grouped together.
- **Figure & ground:** all parts of a zone can be interpreted as both object and background.
- **Induced movement:** a reference pattern formed by certain structures that enables the perception of objects.
- **Periodicity (periodicity):**

⁴⁵ Group of German psychologists who, around 1920, devoted themselves to the study of how the cognitive process takes place that leads from a set of image points to the perception of objects as whole entities. In particular, the first studies were those of MAX WERTHEIMER, WOLFGANG KOHLER and KURT KOFFKA. In German, the word '*gestalt*' means form, structure, but also 'whole').

It is therefore appropriate to organise the user interface, elements and content according to *gestalt* principles to reduce the cognitive load on the user and improve perception. A basic good practice may be to use the law of proximity to place logically connected elements together and use the similarity principle to achieve consistency in the user interface or composition.

4.2.4. *Typography*

Text is the main ingredient of most interfaces. Typographic choices become important not only for readability but also for the personality of the digital product.

The *typography* of the product indicates the maturity of its design and is the relevant part of the UX.

Digital text enjoyed through devices must first and foremost be readable (it is more affatically readable than on paper), otherwise it really does not matter if the font with which the text is typed is beautiful and elegant and if it reflects the typeface of the typical user, if it does not read it does not work.

But readability is a rather relative parameter, of course, depending on the characteristics of each specific font such as *Kerning*, the weight of the individual characters, the contrast between the parts of the letters, the presence or absence of grace marks, in short, the anatomy of the individual symbols, but the individual criterion of readability is the size of the text.

A good digital product the readability of a text must be balanced for each specific user, it must therefore adopt the technique of *dynamic type*, i.e. the possibility for the user to set the size of the text according to his or her needs, and consequently it should ensure the alignment of the entire layout. The other rule to be followed is not to use so many different fonts or so many variants of the same font within the same product. So many *fonts* put together, especially on the same screen for the sake of 'embellishment', create unnecessary noise, distract the user and draw excessive attention to themselves. It is therefore necessary to avoid using several *fonts* within the same product, unless changing *fonts* is one of the product's main functions (think of a *word processor* or *reading software*). Typography, also indicates the hierarchy of contents, guides us from the beginning to the end of the process and also within the text itself, for instance by typographically distinguishing titles from notes.

We also think about the message the chosen *font* communicates and whether it fits with the overall vision of our product. For example, it would not make sense to use a font with heavy, sophisticated gothic strokes if our *app* has modernity as one of its cornerstones.

In the early days of graphical user interfaces and IT, typography appeared careless or even casual, but over the years the maturity of more careful and conscious *typography* design, thanks also to the increasing compatibility of *browsers*, the diffusion of standard *web fonts as far as the web is concerned* and genuine font management systems as far as application development is concerned.

4.2.5. Colours

Colour is another powerful tool to indicate to the user the correct use of the interface, as well as to express the personality of the product. Colour, when applied well, brings vitality and provides the application and its contents with visual continuity. The use of colour also helps to build hierarchy, e.g. by playing with hue, saturation and their combinations you can make a navigation bar more prominent in the user's eye

of the other, highlighting a button in a given feature group or highlighting the active/passive, on/off status of interactive elements such as *switches* widely used in configuration screens.

When designing the colour palette of an *app*, for example, the portability of the mobile device, through which the app is used, must be taken into account.

Colour palette used in the *app Have You Ever*, a quiz game for iOS developed as an educational project within the Apple Developer Academy.

In order to rule out uselessness of our digital products, we avoid situations where the only factor determining a decision is the choice between red and green. Colours do not always communicate the same things, colour, contrary to what one might think, is not the universal medium, in different cultures it takes on different meanings. In China and Japan, for example, white connotes mourning and this is a possible complication because in the West current design *trends* favour an abundance of white. Another example is the fact that in China the colour red indicates something positive and green something negative ⁴⁶ in total opposition to the almost universal perception of these two colours in the rest of the world.

But by carefully analysing our typical users, we should not go wrong. As well as form/background relations based on *gestalt* theory, the

⁴⁶ In this regard, I invite readers in possession of an iOS device to set the location of their *device* on China and see how this setting affects the Stock Exchange/Stocks *app*.

combinations between the background colour (background) and the figure on it can have different yields; white backgrounds tend to darken and may even affieolve colours conversely black backgrounds tend to brighten colours.

The golden rule for balanced design is always not to dare, too many colours, like too many fonts distract and confuse the user.

Application example of the colour *palette* shown in the previous image.

4.2.6. Control elements

Affin order for the user to operate product functionalities, *apps* have control elements. These elements of the digital product/service UI represent the central pivot of interactivity.

Commands and controls in an *app* explain what it can do and provide the power to realise these possibilities. Digital controls can take different forms and principles, which are also constantly evolving and expanding: *checkboxes*, *radio buttons*, *twists*, *scrolls*, *drop-down menus*, *list boxes*, *text boxes*, *spin boxes*, *search bars*, *notifications* and more. It is important that controls communicate their interactivity, producing *feedforward* and *feedback* usually through colour, animation or sound. With the development of *multi-touch* technology (evolution of the touch screen) many commands and controls of *apps* or sites have dematerialised, these have been replaced by gestures and this must be taken into account when creating controls.

Feedback

Feedback, as commonly used, is an indication that something has happened and should occur with each interaction with the interface. If there is no immediate *feedback*, users will repeat the action they have just done. This can cause problems, such as accidentally buying a product twice or in the case of *industrial design* if applied to dangerous machinery such a failure could even result in death or injury.

Creating the appropriate *feedback* is the designer's task, as well as determining how quickly the product or service will respond and in what manner. Related to *feedback* is *feedforward*.

The feedforward

Feedforward is a form of suggestion is a visual convenience that helps communicate to users what the possible interactions are and what to expect from them; it helps the user better understand how a given interaction works and adapt to it by being able to understand what will happen before performing an action.

The *feedforward* pushes users through the correct sequence of actions so that they can avoid confusion and better achieve their goals (which then if everything has been done correctly are also the design goals). It is therefore the designer's job to help users with what is going to happen and to suggest what to do, even through simple messages such as "*be careful, look here!*", "*you can leave it here*" or "*push it a little further*". Often these are really subtle details that the user might not even notice or perhaps use and not remember that little *hints* helped them. It is something subtle, but powerful. The *payoff* can be enormous when the *feedforward* is executed in an efficacious manner.

In the discussion, we will not sofflter ourselves in analysing all the possible components, which often vary and are exclusive to one or another operating system, but rather we will analyse the basic control elements common to all platforms, clarifying their use and warning against common mistakes that can be made.

Slider

Sliders, or *sliders* in English, are ideal for qualitative values such as brightness, volume, colour selectors, and so on. Never use sliders to select specific numerical values, in such cases, sliders are frustrating and ineffective. Just think of a situation where by means of a *slider* we wanted to select a specific value on a scale, let us assume that we wanted to select the value 6 on a scale ranging from 1 to 10, it could happen that we would stop the cursor on an immediately preceding or following value (5 or 7 for example) and this would cause a state of frustration in the user. Such a thing would not be attributable to the user's lack of skill in centring the cursor on the correct value, rather it would represent a clear design error on the part of the *designer*.

Check Box

It represents the selection or non-selection of a choice. Typically, it has the appearance of a square (rhombus or circle) with a label next to it. The square may contain a cross (or other mark), the presence or absence of which denotes the status of the choice. It may also look like a button pressed or not pressed, a button with a light on or off, or a *switch*.

In its internal state it has a Boolean value (selected or not selected). Sensitive to *mouse click* or touch. When activated, the button's state reverses (from selected to unselected or vice versa).

The programme can query the button to find out its status. It can appear in an interface individually or in groups. In a group of several *check boxes*, each can be selected independently: the options are not mutually exclusive. Due to its nature, it is typically used in configuration screens.

Radio button

Represents a single choice in a set of mutually exclusive choices. Similar in appearance to the check box. Radio buttons are used in groups, in a group at any one time only one choice can be selected (selecting a new choice automatically deselects the previous one).

Dropdown Menu

When there are usually many options, such as choosing a country, year of birth or car manufacturer, a drop-down menu is the perfect component to use. However, if you only have a few options, consider using *radio* buttons or *sliders*. If you have a very long drop-down menu with many options, then consider adding a search or filter to allow the user quick access to the option they need.

Buttons

A command button, or *command button* in English, is an element, typically rectangular with rounded corners and a description inside. Interaction with buttons has historically been one of the fundamental parts of the *user experience* for digital products. The form of a *command button* is not limited to the rectangular shape alone. The only interaction requirement for a *command button* is that the user can execute a command by 'pressing it', i.e. by *clicking the* mouse or *tapping* on the screen. Given its nature, images and background areas can also function as buttons. When pressed, buttons generally undergo a graphical change that mimics a pressed button in addition to performing a predetermined task.

Button size

If the interface you are designing for is a touch display, it is very important to size the elements appropriately. Having to avoid one element to select another can be frustrating and choosing an unwanted option can even change the entire user experience. Adding an abundance of 2 mm between elements is a good rule of thumb to avoid problems. Going more specific, the *Apple Human Interface Guidelines* recommended that developers use elements with a minimum size of 44 pixels wide by 44 pixels high while the *Microsoft Windows Phone UI Design and Interaction Guides* suggested a *target* size of 34 pixels by 26 pixels.

Text fields

A *text* box or *text area* is a graphic control that allows the user to enter or edit textual information that will be used by the programme.

It is represented by a rectangle (of any size), separated from the rest of the interface by borders. Usually a vertical blinking line, called a cursor, is also shown, indicating where the typed characters will be inserted. They provide for the insertion of either a single line or multiple lines of text; if text is expected to exceed the size of the object, scroll bars are typically displayed.

Gesture

Tap, double tap, long press, swipe and drag, swipe away, pinch to zoom; these are all ways to interact with the system, the invisible commands we can execute without touching any particular key. If the system is prepared for this language, it will understand us.

Invisible controls are very useful to 'thin' the interface from numerous buttons: press and hold an image and it will reveal commands or buttons to share, save or bookmark the item.

This type of interaction works exactly like the natural world: we rotate or scroll a document as if it were a sheet of paper, *touch* enables the reproduction of natural gestures to which the user is accustomed regardless of the digital context in which we are. This familiarity with gestures and movements means that the user proceeds intuitively when exploring the functionalities of an *app*, searching for functions by reproducing gestures that are natural to him. In this context, the *designer* must be good at anticipating customers' needs by 'making them find' the functions and flows of use precisely where they are most congenial and natural to them.

If applied well, gestural interfaces can really make dialogue with the system faster and more natural.

4.3. Interface design

After the analysis and having identified flows, actions, paths, contents and hierarchical structure of the project pages, we move on to the design of the individual interfaces with which users will interact to satisfy their needs. The design of interfaces, which is the responsibility of the *UI designer*, sometimes mistakenly confused with the design of the user experience, which is the responsibility of the *UX designer*, is the final part of the *visual design* process that starts with a deep understanding of the users and the project being implemented.

Every project is different: it has users with different needs and expectations, different *business* and *marketing* goals, and a unique value to communicate. For this reason, there are no design practices that if followed to the letter will ensure the success of a digital project; each one represents a new challenge and a new opportunity for the *designer* to create something useful and enjoyable to use. There are, however, rules and principles that are deeply rooted among *designers* and widely applied in countless situations that it is always important to consider as a guide in the transition of interfaces from draft to complete design. There are the nine heuristics of usability by Nielsen and Molic h⁴⁷, the eight golden rules of interface design by Ben Shneiderman ⁴⁸, the principles of interaction design by Bruce T ognazzini⁴⁹ or ranging in industrial *design*, the ten principles of good *design* by Dieter Rams ⁵⁰.

4.3.1. Some principles for good interface design

It is important, before starting to design interfaces, to fix in the mind some of the fundamental principles of the above-mentioned lists which, if followed and

⁴⁷ J. NIELSEN, R. MOLICH, *Heuristic evaluation of user interfaces*, 1990 in AV.VV., *Proc. ACM CHI'90 Conf.* 249-256, Seattle Washington, 1-5 April 1990.

⁴⁸ B. SHNEIDERMAN, C. PLAISANT, *Designing the User Interface: Strategies for Effective Human-Computer Interaction*, Pearson, 2009.

⁴⁹ B. TOGNAZZINI, C. PLAISANT, *Tog on Interface*, Addison-Wesley Professional, 1992.

⁵⁰ D. RAMS, *Less But Better*, Gestalten, 2014.

tested several times when designing with interfaces in front, they are a valuable aid in not losing sight of the goal of creating something that meets user needs and achieves business objectives with a user experience that is simple, intuitive, fluid but also pleasant, aesthetically pleasing and memorable.

The principles of good interface design follow four main objectives:

- **Enabling Users to Control Interfaces**
efficacious instil a sense of mastery in users, which makes them feel at ease; as a result, they learn faster and acquire a sense of confidence in the created environment sooner.
- **Reducing cognitive load:** cognitive load is the amount of mental processing required of users to use a product. This load must be kept to a minimum, so that users do not have to think too much, otherwise they will get tired and, in the worst case, abandon the project.
- **Maintaining the consistency of interfaces:** a design consistency is intuitive and thus relates to the previous objective. Consistency is instrumental in building very usable and easy-to-learn interfaces, where users can transfer their learned knowledge to other points of their navigation or even to other websites or applications.
- Making **interactions comfortable:** everything that is not help users and avoid any form of friction that may be distracting, disruptive, interruptive or hinder interaction. *User-friendly* interfaces must be produced, that is, interfaces that encourage exploration and discovery without fear of negative consequences.

4.3.2. The metaphor of the page

Since its inception, the web has been accompanied by the metaphor of the page, adopted to make an unfamiliar environment such as the *World Wide Web* familiar. But this metaphor, certainly very useful and efficacious for this purpose, has in fact led to a major misinterpretation of the new medium

of communication which, in contrast to pages, is fluid, interactive and interdependent. Considering pages as a unit of measurement has also created quite a few problems in estimating and quantifying the time needed to design a site: estimates cannot be made on the basis of the number of pages, they must be made on the functionalities and contents that compose them, i.e. their complexity.

Today, the metaphor of web pages is even more anachronistic: the distinction between the digital world and the physical world is increasingly disappearing, becoming one, and it is in this transition between digital and physical spaces that user experiences are built. With a multitude of devices, channels and touchpoints through which experiences unfold, one can no longer remain anchored to the design of something that is static and confined like a page. It is necessary to look beyond the page, to think omnichannel, to consider mixed physical-digital spaces; in short, it is necessary to embrace a systemic vision. The complex web of relationships between humans and objects, placed in their context, has become the foundation upon which most if not all user experiences must be built.

This is why we speak of the UX ecosystem as '*a set of interdependent relationships between components within an information environment*⁵¹', as defined by Dave Jones. Designers certainly have to be very attentive to small details but it is even more important that they have a broad view of the product, which is used together with other products and influenced by the context of use.

But to build interfaces designed to be served by a multitude of connected devices, it is time to evolve and move from the page to a systemic and 'atomic' vision.

4.3.3. Atomic Design

Atomic design is a modern methodology for creating design systems from the smallest elements that make up interfaces, called atoms, which combined together create molecules, which make up organisms,

⁵¹ D. JONES, *Design for Thriving UX Ecosystem*, (uxmag.com 14 August 2012) [last accessed: 19.04.2020].

which combine to create the *layout*, which declined into *templates* (specific to each *touchpoint* provided for the product/service) ultimately creates the pages. It is a hierarchical way of organising and designing the various parts of user interfaces created by Brad Frost ⁵². Starting from the atom, one can create all the fundamental *design* elements, which allow one to build any part of a digital project. The advantage of this approach to organic design is to promote consistency and scalability.

By creating small elements that are combined to create progressively more complicated elements, atomic design can ensure the consistency of layouts and pages, which is increasingly difficult and important to ensure due to the increasing number of devices, browsers and contexts of use at a dizzying rate.

This contextual complexity cannot be reflected in a proliferation of digital designs, but must necessarily be solved with a single design that can expand as the number of devices increases. *Atomic design* is a response to these needs, which in recent years is revolutionising the way user interfaces are conceived, designed and even developed.

4.3.4. Design system

The design *system*, using Roberto Falcone's definition:

⁵² B. FROST, *Atomic Design by Brad Frost Make and Maintain Great Design Systems*, Brad Frost, 2016.

"is a shared tool that serves as a common vocabulary and universal reference system throughout the design, development and evolution process of a digital product ⁵³".

Traditionally, *deliverables* produced by designers for development have consisted of monolithic, static, pixel-perfect files for the most commonly used resolutions. For a long time, we have been regular users of digital products skilfully produced through this method.

The proliferation of fruition devices and their resolutions, however, quickly showed the limitation of a page template approach, which is particularly inefficacious in cases where a complex digital product is articulated over several *touchpoints* ⁵⁴ and different platforms.

A common habit among designers to reduce processing times has also always been to draw on previously realised files to realise a new design. A typical characteristic of modern digital products, however, is their mutability over time, due to the constant flow of evolution involving iterative cycles of enriching functionality and *testing* different interface solutions through *A/B testing*.

In such a context, a static file becomes obsolete almost immediately and some design elements may have become deprecated, while others designed from scratch may not yet have been approved and shared with the development *team*. This type of situation forces developers from time to time to check with *product managers* and/or *designers* *what the* current, up-to-date version of a *feature* or interface is, generating inefficiency in the work of both designers and developers.

Furthermore, as the number of people working on the same *design* project increases, it becomes increasingly easy for communication breakdowns to occur. In fact, it is not uncommon for different figures to refer to the same *design* element by different names.

⁵³ R. FALCONE, *Design System*, in D. BOTTÀ, *User eXperience Design: Designing valuable experiences for users and companies*, Milan, Ulrico Hoepli, 2018.

⁵⁴ "The touchpoint is where brands and customers come into contact. Touchpoints represent the doors that enable us to reach a goal" from M. C. LAVAZZA, *Touchpoint! Touchpoint! Touchpoint!*, (www.mclavazza.it 28 December 2016) [last accessed: 19.04.2020].

Recently, *designers* and developers of user interfaces have therefore started to adopt a more systematic, modular and hierarchical, pattern-driven methodology: the '*design system*'. Interfaces are broken down into smaller, reusable modules which, combined through a system of rules and hierarchy, then go on to compose the interface in its entirety, subverting the traditional paradigm.

From typographical styles to interaction elements, from colour palettes to code conventions (e.g. nomenclature of *design* variables), a *design system* brings together in a comprehensive and usable manner all the elements that contribute to the realisation of a digital product and allows a *team* to be always aligned and grow with a solid foundation, especially when it incorporates within it the guiding principles and strategic vision of the product, such as Lonely Planet's RIZZO, Shopify's POLARIS or IBM's CARBON, which are some of the most comprehensive examples of design systems currently implemented.

The first *step* in creating a *design system* is to clearly state the company's *value proposition*, its long-term vision and the philosophical and cultural values on which it is based. The second step is to inventory and formalise any pre-existing material, rationalising what is duplicated or inconsistent in order to create a solid *repository* that eliminates all forms of ambiguity. Next we define the visual elements of *brand* expression (logo, colour palette, typographic scale, iconography, illustrations, etc.) and then the components of the user interface: grids, buttons, control and interaction elements, input fields, micro-interactions, etc. The last crucial step is to establish a system of shared rules by which the interaction and branding elements are put together to build the final interfaces, such as *Atomic Design*.

Constantly updated and maintained, a *design system* becomes a solid bridge between the teams working on a digital product, establishes a shared language that accelerates the process of realisation and evolution of the product itself, and helps to eliminate the so-called 'design debt': that overabundance of styles, components and conventions that cannot be reused, are obsolete and inconsistent with each other. *Design systems*, in short, represent an excellent paradigm shift in the design and

development of a digital product, with enormous advantages for both practitioners and users.

The members of the different teams share the same design principles and choose a common design and development model, promoting clarity and consistency in everything they undertake and thus reducing time, cost and effort compared to the past.

Users, on the other hand, gain a sense of familiarity, trust and security towards the product which, through a language that is always harmonious and cohesive, guarantees an experience that remains recognisable, coherent and usable on every device that can be used.

CHAPTER 5: IMPLEMENTATION

As we have seen throughout the discussion, the *UX Designer* is required to move transversally between various disciplinary domains ranging from the humanities to design, from marketing to computer science. Such a multi-disciplinary training is also useful to give the UX the necessary elasticity to deal from case to case with domains, environments and technologies that are also very different from one another; in fact, the ability to maintain a solid reference to the method is required, while adapting (and adapting it) to the specificities of each individual project.

Usually before start-up there is a customer, or an internal *stakeholder* within your company, who requires a site because they have started with a certain project or have yet to start and need an *app*; the requests will be the most diverse. Let us analyse the operational steps and the numerous *deliverables* required of a *UX designer*. Peter Morville, in an interesting article from 2009, well describes 55 types of *deliverables* required in a UX process and Andrea Soverini drew up a *check list* of as many as thirty activities⁵⁶ that are the responsibility of the *UX designer*.

In this chapter we will analyse the implementation part and the *deliverables* related to this phase, always keeping in mind that we are within an iterative process and what is described here may represent one of the intermediate iterations or the final *output*.

5.1. Brief reference to the UCD

This is the phase in which all information is acquired and points such as objectives and the resources to achieve them are set. The information gathered in this phase will undergo necessary adjustments in the course of planning; the

⁵⁵ P. MORVILLE, *User Experience Deliverables*, (semanticstudios.com 27 January 2009) [last accessed 19.04.2020].

⁵⁶ A. SOVERINI, *UX Project Checklist*, (uxchecklist.github.io) [last accessed 20.04.2020].

project objectives are reviewed in the light of meetings with users and contractors.

In this phase we will apply the UCD's own working method to which we will combine the specific application method for *mobile*, both described in the previous chapters.

At the end of one of the iterations envisaged by the UCD methodology, we will have well defined the characteristics of our user, we will have completed the *user research* (we will probably have *personas*, *proto-personas* or a target market), we will have well defined a concept, user scenarios, we will have chosen the information architecture and started preliminary *user testing* activities.

Insight into information architecture

After gathering all the information, observing and analysing the data, the foundations of AI are built. For digital products, the complex work carried out on the information, invisible during fruition, is fundamental to the success of a good product.

Creating a good information architecture is an investment that guarantees good content retrieval, allows it to grow harmoniously over time, and makes it easier to use depending on the tools. By AI we mean the complex organisation of both project and product content. The organisation of project content will also facilitate the creation of *deliverables* such as documentation, *design book*, style guide or *pattern* guide. The organisation of product content, on the other hand, is the basis for navigation systems; in the *app*, *one* navigates according to the initial layout decided by the designer.

Content organisation systems can be infinite: as many as there are facets of human thought. Hypertext has also arrived to complicate everything. With the printed page, information was enjoyed in a linear fashion, in the digital world with hypertext, things change: page A is no longer just followed by page B, but C, D, E; rather, the content has become fluid and is transformed according to the relationships contained within it.

5.2. Creating interfaces

We will now go into a more detailed description of the implementation phase of the information in our possession which leads us, together with the support of the *visual design team*⁵⁷, to the creation of the final interfaces.

5.2.1. User Flow

The first step to start creating user interfaces is to define what users will have to do within them to achieve their goals or satisfy their needs. It is a matter of making explicit step by step, in a different manner with respect to an *experience map*, how the user interacts with the interface; how, consequently, the interface reacts; what the interface allows the user to do. The concept of flow presupposes the movement of users between the various interface components in a sequence of linked actions and reactions. Defining all the possible paths of this movement, how many steps are required, what directions it may take and also what outcomes it may have is crucial in order to circumscribe the most important functional aspects of the design and individual pages according to the user and his or her problems to be solved.

Too often, we focus prematurely on page design and information architecture, whereas we should focus first on the flows that must be supported by projects. Designing flows linked to clear objectives puts the user before the project and thus creates a positive *user experience* and better results for the *business*.

The definition of the flows and actions that must take place within user interfaces can be expressed textually, with an approach very close to the *storytelling* of use cases or use scenarios, or visually, with a

In very large and structured companies, this *team* may consist of hundreds of people (think of a car manufacturer, for example), but in the world of mobile *app* development, it is often represented by a small group of people mainly dedicated to the *User Interface*, perhaps affiaching external agencies for issues such as logo and *graphic design*. In small realities, typically in the *StartUp* world, we may find ourselves in the condition in which the entire *team* is made up of one person, the *UI Designer*, and even his or her figure coincides with that of the *UX Designer*.

approach close to the developers' mental models with flowcharts. Which method to choose depends on several factors, including the complexity of the flows to be made explicit and the degree of collaboration with the development *team*. *There is* also another tool that is an intermediate route between the previous two, namely the creation of *user stories*, which combine a *human-centred* approach to development requirements and are the core components of the agile methodology. I personally recommend starting with *user flows* based on flow diagrams and then finding confirmation in *user stories*, which should basically tell the story of the flow diagrams.

All these tools have the common goal of helping the *team* to focus on the users and their objectives and to move more easily to the next task of defining and organising the product content.

Flow diagrams

The flowchart represents the sequence of operations that users perform while interacting with a system. A diagram shows the steps in the process the user takes to reach his goal and all the paths that this path may take. The difference with the user path mapped in an *experience map* or *journey map* is that the actions represented by the diagram include only those that occur with the product or service, excluding all external factors.

This diagram is very useful for *UX designers* to quickly assess whether the process to be followed by the users is efficient or too long or tortuous and thus in need of modifications and improvements. It is also very useful for collaborating with developers as it indicates all the states the system can assume. The flowchart can be considered the first visual representation shared with the whole *team* of how the idea that emerged from the conception phase will be developed. This tool will save the entire *team* time in the later stages by visually tracing each step of a user's flow of actions. This ensures that no aspect in the design, requirements or code is forgotten, thus limiting subsequent corrections and iterations.

When trying to describe verbally all the paths a user might take, it is very likely to forget some less common cases

or a few exceptions. Dedicating time to mapping everything in a flowchart, on the other hand, forces one to think about all possibilities. In order to construct an efficacious flow chart, one fundamental rule must be followed, namely striving to construct complete user flows, but with as little complexity as possible. That is, it is important that all the details are there, but without including superfluous information or information extraneous to what is being mapped, focusing on the details that are important for the purpose of the diagram and for those who will have to use it.

The flow chart can be an excellent basis for verifying that the design is supporting all interactions and all states that interfaces can assume and can be used as a basis for constructing *screen flows* or *wireflow*⁵⁸.

5.2.2. Sketches on paper

The first rule to start designing user interfaces is to start by working with low fidelity: concentrating too much on details, especially in the early stages, can lead to a great loss of time when revising the project. Making an idea visual and concrete quickly encourages it to be shared with the rest of the *team*, the client and the users so that it can then be discussed and possibly modified or improved.

Dan Roam asserted that

"visual communication has enormous potential and allows problems to be solved much more quickly e59", so a simple drawing on paper, which does not focus on details, allows many ideas to be produced in a short time and gives everyone the freedom and ease to modify the design even entirely and for countless

⁵⁸ P. LAUBHEIMER, *Wireflows A UX Deliverable for Workflows and Apps*, (www.nngroup.com 4 December 2016) [last accessed: 19.04.2020].

⁵⁹ D. ROAM, *The Back of the Napkins: Solving Problems and Selling Ideas with Pictures*, Portfolio Hardcover, 2008.

times in a short time. They are sketches on paper to which no one 'affes ⁶⁰' and therefore easy to trash. There is no need to be an artist or to be able to draw very well, it is important to represent the idea, words, lines and simple shapes are enough to draw low-fidelity interfaces. In fact, to compose any kind of drawing you only need to be able to make basic shapes (dots, lines, rectangles, circles, ovals) and some very basic figures (a house, a cloud, arrows, arcs, spirals). All the shapes we need to sketch a *personas*, an interface or even a logo on paper are already in front of our eyes. While it is true that the blank sheet of paper may paralyse some, it is also true that you can use predefined page templates, different even by device, printable and ready to use. Finally, you can also use *stencils* to avoid drawing icons, for example. The important thing is to always consider the main rule, you don't need the perfect icon or drawing but only the idea, so adopt the method that allows your ideas to flow without distracting from the details. Building interfaces from sheets of paper allows you to design quickly, to get to paper prototypes as soon as possible and, consequently, also to effect usability tests with users soon.

5.2.3. *Wireframe*

Low-fidelity user interface design is realised and defined at a higher level of detail with *wireframes*. *Wireframes* are visual representations of the page skeleton that show the basic layout, structure, navigation and all major elements. They are easily recognisable by the style of the blocks, the sometimes use of lines instead of text and crossed-out rectangles to represent placeholders for images. They are also devoid of colours (only grey scales are allowed), particular text fonts (it is recommended to use only one and standard), logos and any other

⁶⁰ The human component is very difficult to manage in a *team of creatives*, but the *UX designer lead* must also be able to manage the whole *team* and the individual *designers*. Think, for example, of delegating a complex job that involves a considerable commitment in terms of hours, and then think of having to tell one's collaborator that this work has to be, for one reason or another, completely trashed. A *designer* is emotionally attached to their creations, and seeing the product of hours of work and effort trashed can be frustrating. The experienced *UX designer will* also have to manage this emotionality by trying not to affect his or her products, but will have to apply rational reasoning to them based on experience, method and technique.

graphic element. They are often compared to the design of a house, where one can easily see the structural placement of plumbing, electrical and other building elements without including any interior *design* elements. Similarly, in a *wireframe*, an *app* is designed on a structural level by placing content and functionality according to user needs and paths.

The main reason for producing *wireframes* is that without graphic and aesthetic elements, and thus in the absence of potential distractions, it is possible to focus on the distribution of elements and spaces, the hierarchy between contents, the available functions and thus, more generally, on usability and user experience.

Wireframes help connect the information architecture to *visual design* processes by showing possible paths between pages created by various links; they clarify the visualisation of particular types of information and intended functionality in the user interface; they help align design and development *teams* on the project code; and they also play an important role in defining the responsiveness of interfaces.

Example of *wireframe* used for the development of *Waller61*, an *app* for the simultaneous management of several Bitcoin wallets.

Last but not least, they make content production more efficient. Some argue that to design *wireframes* are not

⁶¹ *Waller* is a prototype *app*, developed by the *Made in Chain team* (composed of V. ACETO, V. AJELLO and P. MAURIELLO as *Software Developer*, C. BARBATO as *Business & Communication Manager*, F. FRESILLI and V. STILE as *UI & UX Designer*) as part of the Apple Developer Academy 2017-2018 course in Naples. The code has been freely distributed on the GitHub platform: V. ACETO, *Waller - A prototype app to manage and test Bitcoin*, (github.com/vinzaceto/madeInChain) [last access: 20.04.2020].

I personally subscribe to this second line of thought and believe that it is worthwhile to include texts as close to final versions as possible, not so much to facilitate their use within the *design team*, but rather to be as clear and explanatory as possible when sharing them with other product *teams* and with the outside world. This second path therefore allows the definition of page structures built on the needs of communication, the opposite entails the risk of subsequently limiting communication in order not to ruin the harmony and aesthetics of the *layout*, arriving at the paradox of creating a *layout unable to* accommodate the definitive content. It is better not to run these risks, especially multiplied by the need, now common to many digital projects, to provide for display on different devices. In the event that content is not yet available, one can use that of a competitor or content that is at least similar in structure.

Wireframes are the basis on which *visual design* is built. For this reason, since they do not have to represent the final result, the principle of simplicity and low fidelity applies more to identifying, correcting navigation problems and quickly redesigning the layout or weight of elements. At this level, it must still be possible to experiment, to build several *layouts* for the same page and also test them with users before the addition of graphic details makes changes much more time-consuming. Remember that we are within an iterative process, it must still be possible to accept drastic changes from *stakeholders*. *Wireframes* are therefore a tool that ensures the sustainability of an iterative design process.

Gathering feedback with wireframes

Gathering targeted feedback on the structural elements of interfaces often requires explaining the role of *wireframes*, because they can be a difficult tool for non-experts to understand. It must be clear and obvious to those involved that they do not represent the finished project, and here

because it is better to keep them low (or at most medium) fidelity and as simple as possible, or the risk of misunderstanding will increase. In many cases it may be really difficult for the audience to understand the relationship between the *wireframes* and the final design, so one must carefully consider to whom one presents them. Presenting *wireframes* accompanied by *visual design*, even just a couple of *mock-up* images, can be essential to explain this link; including notes in *wireframes* to explain certain parts can also facilitate understanding. It is possible to construct *wireframes* with pen and paper or address specific *software*. The best known and most widely used are AXURE, SKETCH and UXP IN ⁶². The choice between the two options must first be made taking into account the complexity of the project; for the design of a simple single-function *app*, schematics on paper might suffice. It might be enough to transfer the design to the *visual designer* who will have to complete it with the graphic part. For the evaluation of the tool to be adopted, one must then ask whether the paper *wireframes* combined with the *visual design to be* produced will be sufficient to transfer all the necessary information to the development *team*. *Wireframes* are often used to define and transfer, for example, the rules of page responsivity and thus to design page structures that take into account the different views for the intended *touchpoints*. Difficilmente design the graphic *layouts of* all pages for all the *touchpoints* of a project, even a moderately complex one: this would greatly expand both the *effort* required and the production time of the graphic part. In this case, the use of *software* becomes necessary for the *UX designer* to be able to edit and manage a large number of interfaces. Although they may seem tedious to create, and thus appear almost an unnecessary additional step in interface design, *wireframes* in the long run save design time and prove to be truly indispensable for several reasons. First and foremost, they help create a better user experience because they allow you to remain in a state of mind of solving user problems, thus putting usability and experience ahead of everything else. They help focus on the functional details that can really make a huge difference in the user experience. A very good example is the *wireframes* related to the user registration process;

⁶² UXPIn from UXPIn Inc., is a comprehensive platform for *UX Designers*, enabling the creation and content sharing, (uxpin.com) [last accessed: 19.04.2020].

consider in detail all the error messages of a form; soff consider how to reassure the user, who at this stage of sharing sensitive data might be afraid of making a mistake. Here it is important to decide whether or not to maintain on-page content: to leave the user with only the fields strictly necessary to fill in the form (e.g. by showing a *pop-up* screen), isolating him/her from the context to avoid distraction, or to provide guidance without leaving the previous context? Providing users with clear *feedback* to avoid getting lost is of paramount importance.

5.3. Visual Design

The work on the interfaces of the *UX designer* generally ends with the production of *wireframes* and, for the completion of the project, there is a collaboration with a visual *designer* who will design the visual part. In smaller agencies, for reasons of economies of scale and cost containment, or in *start-ups*, for reasons here related to control over the process, the *UX designer* and *UI designer* are often represented by a single person. The collaboration between a UX design expert and a *visual design* expert is crucial for building a good user experience ⁶³. The role of the *visual designer* is not to add colours and graphical elements at will to the *wireframe*, but to enrich the interfaces rafforing even more the hierarchy of elements, facilitating the scanning and readability of the page, helping the user to identify *feedback* and thus collaborate productively in achieving the final result. In practice, it must make all the principles of user interface design concretely and markedly visible.

A *visual designer* must therefore have considerable sensitivity and knowledge of all the principles of usability; be able to listen to and collaborate with the *UX designer*; but must also be familiar with the principles of *gestalt*, colour theory, *material design* and the fundamental rules of IxD such as Fitts' law.

Visual design is the art and profession of selecting and organising visual elements such as typefaces, images, symbols and colours to convey a message to users. *Visual design* aims to set the hierarchy

⁶³ When the two functions converge on a single figure, in many cases the design part of the UX is sacrificed, if not non-existent.

visual of a page or flow, but also to elicit appropriate emotional responses. The role of the *visual designer* is, in fact, also to add personality to the product or service, giving it a character and appearance consistent with the company. The personality of the design, which must be in line with the brand's identity, can be a differentiator from the competition and "*is fundamental to realising a human-centred visual design capable of moving the people to whom the project is addressed*"⁶⁴.

In the field of *visual design* for *apps*, the tools have also changed radically in recent years. Adobe Photoshop was finally sent *soffitta* along with Adobe Illustrator, software that was not born to design graphics for apps, and their place was taken by modern tools that embrace the logic and needs of apps to design in a responsive, hierarchical and systemic way. Thus, tools such as Sketch, Adobe XD and InVision Studio were born and took hold.

Visual design also has a very important role in ensuring visual consistency between the various page layouts. Today, to ensure this, in addition to the creation of digital guidelines containing elements such as typography, colours, button styles and other elements, a systemic approach is adopted in parallel with the disappearance of the page metaphor. We are in the era of *design systems*, which break down layouts into even very small elements to ensure modularity and scalability.

5.3.1.I mockup

A mockup is a static *wireframe* with much more user interface and visual details. If a *wireframe* is considered a blueprint of a building, a mockup is similar to a real building model. It gives viewers a more realistic impression of what the final *app* will look like, so it is useful for communicating, discussing, collaborating and iterating on projects with team members at a later design stage.

In short, at difference of *wireframes* with grey lines, crossed out rectangles and placeholders, *mockups* are created with more visual detail than the final *app*:

⁶⁴ A. WALTER, *Designing for Emotion*, A Book Apart, 2011

- Rich colours, styles, graphics and typography.
- Buttons and effective texts.
- Content layout and component spacing.
- Navigation graphics.

Why a mockup is important

After explaining the *design* ideas with a *wireframe*, in order to discuss them further and iterate quickly, the *wireframe* must be updated into a model with a higher quality of user interface and visual details, which offers many advantages to the UX process and the team. We can list the advantages:

- **Show project details for better communication:** i

mockups show specific details of the project and will be easier for the *team* to communicate and discuss a specific detail.

- **Easy for customers and stakeholders to understand:** a *wireframe* may require viewers to use their imagination. However, with a better aesthetic appearance, a *mock-up* makes it easier for anyone, including end customers and investors, to understand and get to know the real product.

- **Easy to preview, test and iterate:** a difference of the skeletal *wireframes*, *mock-ups* are much closer to the final product. They are good models to preview, test, find errors and iterate on in advance. The mockup is also a visual documentation of the product style that facilitates developers in their work.

- **Easy to create:** with a good *mock-up* tool, it is easy to create a realistic *mockup*. So a mock-up is absolutely good to use when it is necessary to communicate, discuss, collaborate and iterate on projects with team members or perhaps to use in the *StartUp* environment for promotion to attract investors.

5.3.2. Prototype

An interactive prototype is a simulation or example of what user interaction will be like in the project and is made to effect tests before the application is launched.

Generally, pre-prototypes are also built in the very early stages of design creation, to get feedback from users on ideas, before investing too much time and resources in the final result. Generally, prototyping is when all the pieces of the *design* eventually come together into a unit. Many customers will differ understand a design *until they* see and use the prototype. The form of these prototypes depends both on the resources of the project, the technical skills of the *designers*, and the type of product being designed. If the resources are appropriate, prototypes can be produced that look and behave exactly like the actual final product. Prototypes are the ultimate expression of the *interaction design* vision and the result of the work of the User *Experience Designer* and the *User Interface Designer* and their respective *teams*. Many designers believe that the creation of prototypes is the *design* activity par excellence and that everything that comes before is only a prelude to this phase. I personally think that it is a very important phase, but also that it can become an end in itself if not supported by meticulous work carried out during all phases of the UX process.

Tools for creating a prototype

Interactive prototypes can be made by creatively assembling sketches on paper or by photographing the sheets and assembling a navigable prototype with applications such as MARVEL , POP ⁶⁵ or even INVISION. Much more precise prototypes can also be realised by making static *wireframes* interactive and clickable. The latter solution not only provides greater certainty in the successful transfer of the final design idea to users, but also allows interactions and usability to be tested. All *software* for creating *wireframes* allows interactions to be generated, from very advanced ones with

⁶⁵ POP (Prototyping On Paper), created by the *start-up* Woomoo and later acquired by Marvel Prototyping LTD, is software that allows the creation of simple prototypes from sketch images made on paper (marvelapp.com/pop/) [last accessed 19.04.2020].

AXURE to the more basic ones with SKETCH. In some cases, it is also possible to make use of much simpler tools, such as POWERPOINT or KEYNOTE, which are generally used for making presentations, or even to build functional prototypes, even with spreadsheet *software* such as EXCEL or NUMBERS. The important thing is to choose the tool with which you are able to effect a rapid prototyping of interactions because, after testing with users, it is very likely that adjustments will need to be made quickly.

The choice of the type of prototype depends on the time and resources available and also on the objectives of the tests with users that are to be effected: for testing an idea, even a sketch on paper may suffice, whereas in the case of usability testing, the type of prototype depends on the complexity of the interactions to be submitted to users. Finally, the choice may also be conditioned by how the specifications of the behaviour of the interfaces to user interaction will be transferred to the development *team*. In this case, the assessment as to whether it is advisable to produce a very advanced working prototype must be made by considering the time required to produce it, as opposed to producing a document accompanying the static *layouts* that explains the more complex and onerous interactions to be realised, or to inserting annotations directly on the *wireframes*.

Finally, it is also possible to describe the interactions by joining flow diagrams with *wireframes* declined in the different states, which they can assume depending on the user interaction. This union generates *screen flows* or *wireflows*. The union of the two tools arose because *wireframes* communicate structure and content in a static manner without interactions, while flowcharts describe interactions in detail but are devoid of context of use: together they make it possible to show how the structure or content of pages change as a result of user interactions.

The elements of a *wireflow* are the entry and exit points, all intermediate steps such as user actions, system responses and alternative paths, and the various decision points where there are at least two options to choose from. Software that enables the construction of this particular type of

flowchart is LIGHTS D CHART ⁶⁶, or you can use, the oft-mentioned, SKETCH or OVERFLOW ⁶⁷.

This type of tool fosters strong collaboration between the design team, *stakeholders* and the development team, who can thus visually share user flows and be certain that they are aligned on what the final design will be. Producing a *wireflow* can be the preliminary step in deciding how to assemble a prototype to be tested with users.

One advantage of prototypes, which links us directly to the next topic, is that they can be easily distributed. They can be uploaded to the *web and be* usable via a simple *link* or they can be easily uploaded to designated devices (the product *touchpoints*) and have users try them out.

5.4. Testing

Testing with users is one of the pivotal phases of a user experience project. The results of testing serve to keep the project adherent to reality, detecting difficulties, liking and expectations of users of a site, *app, software* or parts thereof.

Involving end-users in the design in various ways helps the final success of the product. One of these ways is to test the product with people. Steve Krug, referring to *websites*, said '*if you want a great site, you have to test it [...] quickly and easily and also cheaply*⁶⁸'. This statement is all the more relevant when applied to the world of *mobile apps*, since thanks to the numerous prototyping *tools*, the creation and, above all, the distribution of a test product is quick and easy.

But it is crucial to manage test session information well because it can be multiple and complex. Testing is important therefore, but

⁶⁶ Lucidchart from Lucid Software Inc. is a proprietary web-based platform that enables users to collaborate on writing, reviewing and sharing charts and diagrams. Available at (www.lucidchart.com) [last accessed: 19.04.2020].

⁶⁷ Overflow by Protoio Inc. is one of the first flowcharting *software* made specifically for *designer of the digital world* (overflow.io) [last accessed 19.04.2020].

⁶⁸ S. KRUG, *Usability – Identifying and Solving Problems*, Tecniche Nuove, 2010.

it should not be done on a single observation. Statistical value counts and, therefore, the more people who say that, for example, that particular colour makes it difficult to read, the greater the need for intervention. The same rules that guide *design* research also guide testing, we go to users, we talk to them, we note things down.

The entire testing process can be divided into three phases:

1. **planning:** with the choice of approach, the design of times and places and the recruitment of people;
2. **the test activity:** with the development of the guides and facilitation rules;
3. **the analysis of the results:** with the elaboration of recommendations.

5.4.1.Planning

Testing, like virtually all UX activities, is an iterative process that can be repeated several times at various points in the project. In the past, testing was only performed at the end of the process, before release. But testing as a semi-final activity is scarcely efficacious, interventions made just before release always have the effect of a running *bugfix* and are scarcely efficacious.

The pre-release test, *User Acceptance Test* (abbreviated UAT), is important, but it is not conducted on the end users, it is conducted within the *team* to ensure that all customer requirements have been implemented correctly. Testing sessions, on the other hand, can be conducted from the beginning to the end of the project, even before design when the product does not exist. During design, we can test individual parts of the product such as a functionality (the purchase process, a *form*, navigation, etc.), or choose to test the product as a whole.

We can ask people various things, including to understand the system, the concept, the logic of the site; for example to ask what this particular label contains or where they would *tap* for more information when purchasing a product.

Another characteristic of tests is the way they are conducted, i.e. in-person or remote. Remote tests can be a good solution when

there are impediments to direct contact ⁶⁹. The efficacy of these tests, however, is always less than that of a live test session because non-verbal language is lost, a hesitation, an arching of the eyebrow or facial expressions provide important information that can only be grasped in person.

Another modality that is differing is *guerrilla testing*, which consists of analysing people in public places or directly in places common to users, recording their reactions and interviewing them informally. People are thus freer to be themselves and interact in a natural way. Applying this method, however, does not mean neglecting planning; on the contrary, the way in which data is recorded and the way in which it is analysed must be planned and established beforehand.

Planning means how to collect data: in qualitative or quantitative form. Quantitative tests involve numbers, *taps*, the number of times an action is performed. Data is collected numerically and this leads to very sharp results. Qualitative tests, also known as formative tests, work on observing users' choices while using the application. The ultimate goal is to learn, by observing the users, what works and what does not work in our *design*, whether the users succeed in completing an assigned task, thus the expected functioning of the *flows* as intended.

In this type of test, unlike quantitative tests, there is no statistical number of data. There is generally never a sufficiently high number of users to assume that their behaviour represents the entire population, and the issue of recruitment, i.e. subjecting the test to a *target* close to the identified *personas*, becomes important. Recruitment is quite a complex issue because one can decide to choose users similar to those who will use the *app* or different users in case we are interested in a different point of view. In any case, tests should be carried out early and often.

According to Steve Krug, the perfect number of users is between three and four people per test session. This way you will probably encounter all the most significant problems. A second session can be done, perhaps detecting less important problems, and a report can be produced on the same day.

⁶⁹ Think of *apps* designed for markets other than the *design team's* home market, or special environmental or health situations such as the 2019-2020 COVID-19 pandemic.

At the end of the test sessions we will have a lot of material: written, filmed, audio and we will necessarily have to put it in order. The ideal is to act immediately, doing everything on the same day, test people in the morning, highlight the problems and in the afternoon work out the first recommendations. From the material collected, a priority scale must be worked out; 'triage' according to Krug. A system similar to that used in hospital emergency rooms. Thus, problems to be solved immediately are 'marked' with a red sticker, a green one for those to be solved later and a yellow one for those to be solved when there is time.

Examine, based on the scale drawn up, which problems to solve first and how. Leave aside secondary problems, such as those where the user feels an initial difficulties that they can solve themselves. One must at this stage not give in to the temptation to include all the functions reported and requested by people.

5.4.2. Results

The results can be told to the customer, but it can be even more useful to present them to the customer. We can elaborate a *storytelling*, with photos of people and *screenshots* of the main steps of the test. Or explain in a concise and general way the impact the interface had on users.

We can present *screenshots* of pages with data of interest and comments, cleverly alternating between quantitative and qualitative data depending on the context and the people present. We can also show data by means of formal representations such as graphs and text documents or informal ones such as cartoons or animations.

Finally, we have recommendations, which are the consequence of observation. They can come from us or from other users and are the solution to the problem. They are supplemented with data, as we have seen for screenshots, or alternatively a text document can be created explaining the problem, the causes and the solution.

Nevertheless, one should not be in a hurry to overhaul an application that has shown some problems. Many times it is enough just to give

relief or highlighting the right functionality. There is always time to create, but the ability to enhance the existing is certainly more interesting.

5.5. Management

Having reached the end, having tested and iteratively corrected the prototype, it is now time to 'write' the future of our project. Style guides and *design patterns* are the documents that allow us to represent the future of our application. They represent the 'baton' that a good *design team* leaves to those who will come after them or to the *team* itself if they are to continue working on the project or will be called upon to do so in the future.

5.5.1. Style Guide

It originates from the top of the *team* and is shared by everyone involved. It is a fundamental document that is drawn up at the end of the design or *redesign*. It is a document that describes how to maintain and grow the product according to principles and rules of consistency. If you work in a *team*, these guides are a fundamental document for sharing standards. They are also very important because they ensure memory regarding choices that have been made over time, facilitate work sharing, aid training in product management and allow consistency in product growth. Style guides also serve to play in advance by establishing principles and rules on possible future problems.

It may also happen that the style guide does not work, that it is not perceived as a fundamental tool by those in charge of digital communication. There may be many reasons for this: it does not have the correct diffusion within the *team* (often those in charge of a project may tend to diffuse only parts of it in order to gain some, fake, working advantage and/or control over subordinates or other parts of the organisation), it is not coherent or the information is not organised correctly or simply the information has not been updated over time and is therefore inconsistent with the current status of the project.

So in order to maintain a proper style guide, it must be made credible, consultable by all (perhaps even via the *intranet*). It can also be printed if it is deemed to be consulted often and the *design team* works together in the same place.

5.5.2. Design Pattern

It is a repository of solutions to recurring problems in the design of one or more parts of the application. The term comes from the development environment and can be translated as design pattern and can be defined as 'a general design solution to a recurring problem'. It may describe overall aspects (*pattern library*) or parts of interfaces (*component library*) such as the *Tab Bar*, *CollectionView* or *TableView*⁷⁰.

The choice depends on the complexity of the reality in which one works or on market requirements. This is certainly a less diffuseful document than the others, but no less important. For large agencies with a large number of digital products to manage, the *pattern design* document has its advantages: it avoids having to redesign from scratch already affronted solutions and represents the certainty that the *design* adopted remains in line with the company's choices.

As with style guides, *pattern designs* serve to keep the most interesting solutions alive and available to all; even when different people are involved in the project, the solutions found must be tracked to help afford possible unforeseen events that each project will afford.

5.6. Final Delivery

Having almost reached the end of the various project phases, it is now necessary to strengthen the message through presentation. The processes and documents we have analysed are different in nature, some distinctly technical, others more analytical, but for all of them it is the presentation that counts, which can have a decisive influence on the success of the project.

⁷⁰ *Tab Bar*, *CollectionView* and *TableView* are basic elements of iOS user interfaces, specific and customised *patterns* can be defined for these components or affiliate to the patterns defined in the development guidelines provided by Apple itself.

An efficacious presentation, whether narrative or visual, helps to convince and create consensus. A good idea presented badly can become a bad idea. To present a document in the best possible way, we must take into account three fundamental factors:

1. **what:** the type of document;
2. **how:** i.e. the tools and capabilities available;
3. **who:** the target audience.

By combining these three aspects, a good product can be realised. There are documents that can be presented through *links*, through projections, or be drawn on a blackboard or paper. If we are good with drawings or know how to write, we can bring stories to life, if we are technologically capable we can present ingenious, multimedia, living documents. By adapting to the customer, we can also introduce new ways of presentation that take into account the environment, culture or habits of the interlocutor.

Finally, one must break out of rigid corporate stereotypes and also speak with empathy where the situation allows and be as clear and natural as possible. At this stage, in addition to the final *output*, unresolved issues could be presented and submitted for *stakeholder* consultation.

Below we will look at the most common techniques and tools for making efficacious presentations.

5.6.1. Storyboard

It is a document in the form of text and images based on a plot that develops from a starting point to a final epilogue. It is the best tool to present and explain how a process unfolds: such as the path to purchase a product online and consumer behaviour.

The *storyboard* simplifies the communication of complex processes and, in situations where a problem needs to be framed, gives the opportunity to do so from a point of view, that of the user, which generates the action and gives interested cues to the whole *team* to take efficient action in solving it.

5.6.2. Storytelling

This document uses but people's emotions. It tells a process, a dynamic. It documents and communicates the whole process of creation and implementation by bringing into play feelings such as disappointment, indecision, final victory. In this regard, *storytelling is* often given the name *The Hero's Journey*, i.e. the tale of the hero's journey, made of difficulties but always with a happy ending that is represented by the final solution being proposed.

5.6.3. Narrative report

It is the document that encapsulates in narrative form part of the documents developed during the project, from the market analysis to the prototype. It is a report that explains how the project came into being, why it came into being, what the objectives were, the methodology used, the expected results and the results obtained.

A difference from the other documents, there are various *narrative report* documents. Apart from the topics of each individual project, there are common headings applicable to any interactive project design such as title, table of contents, introduction, scenario, objectives, methodology, results, timeframe, manner, recommendations or future steps. A *narrative report* must be written for each of these project components.

Given its nature, this document therefore serves as a critical review of the entire project, the work done, the difficulties encountered and the goals achieved, analysing the project in progress and helping to avoid the same mistakes in the future. For those who work in the *mobile app* world and are used to working with very tight deadlines and very tight conception, design and development cycles, it may be challenging to write it down, but it is an investment for future work.

5.6.4. The scenario

Many of the documents we have seen describe a situation, an action or a process; creating a scenario is like writing a script, which is fundamental to techniques such as *storyboarding*. The scenario, like a film script, has a protagonist (the user in this case) who performs an action, e.g.

complete the registration or perform a search within the content. This action will trigger consequences and solutions that are affronted by documents such as the market analysis (comparing how the user acts when effaccessing competitor *apps*), the map (evaluating the user's behaviour in front of the *app* architecture) or the *process flow*. Without scenario, the story does not come to life, it does not show emotions, and emotions are what support judgement. The more accurately we create context and storyline, the more we avoid providing a final product based only on hypotheses.

5.6.5.Presentation (Keynote, PowerPoint)

It is an information product with a logical structure and sequential progression, but it is usually not self-sufficient, it only comes to life when accompanied by an oral exposition. A good mix of text, graphics and verbal skills is needed to communicate the essentials and get the approval of the team.

The presentation that combines text and image has the greatest communicative and persuasive potential, in fact it increases the learning of a given concept by 80%.

According to Cliff Atkinso n71, according to the principle of signalling, we must avoid generic or incisive titles, avoid *slides* with too much text. According to the principle of segmentation, we must offrire a concise and incisive focus on each topic, one per *slide*; according to the principle of modulation, we must hold the listener's attention by separating the visual element from the sound element, e.g. by writing the question in text form in the *slide* and giving the answer verbally; according to the principle of multimedia, we must make the most of visual language, suggestive images accompanied by something capable of generating expectation, can be more incisive.

One of the fundamental aspects, in order to achieve efficacious presentations, is training. Training in *public speaking*, by repeatedly rehearsing the presentation to be given, taking care of the timing and body language to be displayed

⁷¹ C. ATKINSON, *Beyond Bullet Points: Using Microsoft PowerPoint to Create Presentations That Inform, Motivate, and Inspire*, Microsoft Press, 2005.

during the presentation. In very important contexts it will be necessary to rehearse and rehearse a presentation even for hours.

CHAPTER 6: CHALLENGE-BASED LEARNING

CBL, or *Challenge Based Learning* is an educational *framework* for learning and development based on solving real problems. The theories underlying the *framework* were developed by Apple Inc. during the 'Apple Classrooms of Tomorrow-Today'⁷² project in 2008 and formalised in a *white paper* published in 2009⁷³.

In education CBL

Using *challenges* to frame learning experiences originating from the analysis of reality, groups and individuals exploit experience, internal and external resources, develop a plan and work to find the best solution to cope. It is a journey of experimentation, failure, success. Through this process, the relationship between cause and effect is fully appreciated.

During the challenge, students document their experience using audio, video, images and photography. The ongoing collection of content provides resources for reflection, informative evaluation and documentation of the learning process.

By adding challenges to learning environments, the result is a positive sense of urgency, increased passion and a motivating sense of ownership of what is being done, ingredients often lacking in schools.

In the professional field CBLD

The CBL *framework*, conceived and developed in a purely educational context, has been gradually adapted and used in the world of product development as well, in

⁷² THE APPLE CLASSROOMS OF TOMORROW -TODAY, commonly abbreviated ACOT2 or ACOT2, is a collaborative project between Apple Inc. and the education community to identify essential principles for the 21st century school. A *framework* that identifies efficacious learning and teaching models in the world of technology.

⁷³ M. H. NICHOLS, K. CATOR, *Challenge Based Learning White Paper*, Cupertino, California, Apple Inc., 2008.

especially of products with a high technological and innovative content. This *framework* has been called Challenge Based Learning and Development (abbreviated CBLD). It is an emerging *framework* that combines development and learning in order to better understand all aspects of the process, creating meaningful and valuable products.

Its cyclic nature allows integration with other models including UCD, *Design Thinking*, *Lean Startup* and *Agile*. CBLD provides an open framework that can be customised and contextualised to the specific development needs of each organisation.

6.1. Notions of CBL

The CBL in its most diffusa definition is:

"an efficient and efficacious framework for learning while solving certain real-world challenges. The framework nurtures collaboration to identify Big Ideas, ask thoughtful questions and identify, investigate and solve challenges. CBL helps students gain a deep understanding of the subject area and develop the skills they need to thrive in an ever-evolving world luzione⁷⁴".

The CBL *framework* is divided into three interconnected phases: *engage*, *investigate* and *act*. Each phase includes activities that help move to the next phase. Within each of the phases there are opportunities for mini-cycles of investigation and, if necessary, a return to an earlier phase in an iterative process that in some respects may be similar to the UCD approach. Supporting the entire process is a continuous production of documentation, reflection and sharing.

6.1.1. Engage Phase

During the *engagement* phase, students move from an abstract *big idea* to a concrete, actionable challenge using the process of formulating *essential questions*. The aim is to personally connect with the content

⁷⁴ The Challenge Institute, (www.challengebasedlearning.org) [last accessed 21.04.2020].

academics through the identification, development and ownership of a compelling challenge.

The Big Idea

A big *idea* is a broad theme or concept important to you and to a community that can be explored in many ways. Examples of big ideas include community, relationships, creativity, health, sustainability, spirituality and democracy.

Le essential question

Starting from the analysis of the *Big Idea*, we arrive at the generation of a wide range of essential questions that reflect personal interests and community needs (e.g. "*Why is this important to me?*", or "*What connection is there between this concept and my world?*" etc.). The *essential question* process ends with the identification of a single question that has personal and therefore 'essential' meaning.

The challenge

The *challenge* transforms the *essential question* into a *call to action* to learn more about the topic. A challenge must be immediate, implementable and create excitement. The *engagement* phase ends with the identification of a convincing and implementable *challenge*.

6.1.2. The Investigate stage

From the defined *challenge*, students develop contextualised learning experiences and conduct rigorous, content- and concept-based research to create a basis for viable and sustainable solutions.

Guiding Question

The investigation phase begins with the generation of questions related to the challenge. The questions include everything that needs to be learnt to develop an informed solution to the challenge. The questions are prioritised, creating an outline for the student's journey.

Guiding Activity and Guiding Resource

Any resource or activity that helps answer the guiding questions and develop an innovative, in-depth and realistic solution can be used. Examples of guiding resources include: online content and courses, databases, textbooks and *social networks*. Examples of guiding activities include: simulations, experiments, projects, problem sets, research and games.

Synthesis

Once all guiding questions have been addressed and the results of the guiding activities have been recorded, the students analyse the accumulated data and identify themes.

The investigation phase concludes with reports and presentations demonstrating that the students have addressed all guiding questions successfully and developed clear conclusions that will form the basis for the solution.

6.1.3. The Act phase

In the *act* phase, evidence-based solutions are developed and implemented with a real audience and results are validated. Students combine the desire to differentiate with a demonstration of content mastery.

Solution Concept

After completing the investigation phase, students have a solid basis to begin developing concepts for the solution. Elements for the solution may include plans for an information or training campaign, school or community improvement projects, product development or other activities.

Solution Development

After the *solution concept* is approved, students develop prototypes, experiments and tests. This iterative design cycle will most likely raise new guiding questions that require further research and this will lead back to the investigation phase.

Implementation and Evaluation

After developing their solutions, students implement them, measure the results, reflect on what worked and what did not, and determine their impact on the challenge. Once implementation is complete, students can continue to refine the solution or develop a final synthesis document and share their work with the rest of the world.

CHAPTER 7:

CASE STUDY ROSARIES UM75

This case study examines the development and creation of the ROSARI UM - ROSARY CROWN *app*, and in particular traces the process that led to the creation of the *app* for *watchOS* ⁷⁶.

This process takes place in the context of the Apple Developer Academy, a high-level training course developed through the collaboration between Apple Inc. and the University of Naples Federico II, and was set up in response to a *challenge* proposed by *Apple's Technology Evangelism* ⁷⁷ *Team* headed by Kristie Dickinson ⁷⁸.

Within the specifications required by the *challenge*, we pursued the main objective of the *app*, which is to design an application that aims to bring people closer to a spiritual dimension using an intimate and personal tool such as the Apple Watch.

In order to meet the needs of future users, it seemed natural to use the technique of *User Experience Design* during the requirements analysis and design phases, and *Challenge Based Learning* (commonly abbreviated to CBL) was used as the development *framework*.

7.1. The challenge

After explaining what CBL consists of and its phases, starting with the *Big Idea* that kicked off the CBL '*Apple Watch*' and the *essential question* '*How to*

⁷⁵ ROSARI UM - ROSARY CROWN is an iOS and watchOS app currently on the App Store with more than 10,000 *downloads* and around 1,000 active users on a weekly basis [as of 20.04.2020].

⁷⁶ Operating system for Apple Watch, Apple's *smartwatch*.

⁷⁷ A *Technology Evangelist* is a person who contributes to building a critical mass of support for a given technology and thus helps in the diffusion of technical product standards, usually by showcasing the potential uses and benefits of a technology to help others, and especially developers, understand how they can use it for themselves and their own projects.

⁷⁸ Professor of *Design Thinking* at Boston College Carroll School of Management and previously *Apple Watch Lead, Developer Relations* at Apple Inc.

design great Apple Watch experiences?" we come to the definition of the *challenge* that inspired the creation of ROSARI UM:

"Design a Single Feature app for Apple Watch".

The *timeframe* for the development of the CBL process and thus of the challenge was very limited, just five working days, but by using fast and iterative cycles of analysis, prototyping and testing, we achieved a working beta of our product by the end of the fifth day.

7.1.1. Foreword

Let us start by describing the context: the product conception and development *team* consisted of myself and five colleagues. The wide-ranging cross-skills and the good specialisation of each in specific areas meant that responsibilities were divided among the various *team* members.

The team

- **Ciro Barbato**, bursar, communication and *management* expert was responsible for *project management* and public relations;
- **Dario Abete**, a doctor in aerospace engineering, worked as *software* developer was responsible for the release on the App Store;
- **Marco Regis**, worked as a *software* developer and was responsible for translations into English and Spanish;
- **Alfredo Rizzo**, experienced *front end software* developer was responsible for the development of the iOS application;
- **Mauro Romito**, PhD in computer engineering, an expert and passionate *game developer* worked as a *software* developer and was responsible for the development of the watchOS application;
- And finally me, **Vittorio Stile**, who brought my contribution to the team gained from previous experience in *industrial design* and *graphic design*. I took over the development of the User *Experience* and *User Interface* of the product.

The workplace

Much of the work was carried out in the facilities of the Apple Developer Academy in the university campus of San Giovanni a Teduccio in Naples. The facility, which comfortably allowed for communicating workstations for six people, and the general *layout* of the spaces allowed for constant collaboration between *team* members, who were able to meet in *open* collaborative *areas* equipped with large TVs for presenting content and whiteboards for collaborative *brainstorming* sessions.

A well-designed working environment enables the *team* to generate better ideas in the product definition phase, to make more careful observations in the analysis phase, and to achieve higher productivity in the production phase.

This aspect is often underestimated, but of fundamental importance in modern development paradigms.

The method

For the development of the *user experience* of this application, I made use of the techniques I learnt during the Apple Developer Academy course, my previous work experience and the notions inherent to UCD, contextualising everything in the academic development environment of using CBL as an educational *framework*.

My aim is therefore to propose an innovative approach to the development of the *User Experience* in the mobile environment based on what was formalised previously in the paragraph "Application of the UCD at Mobile ⁷⁹ " and contextualising it within the CBL *framework*.

⁷⁹ Chapter 3, paragraph 3.5.

Here is a schematic representation of my proposed innovative approach to *user experience* development in the mobile environment.

7.1.2. The investigation phase

The investigation phase begins with the generation of questions related to the challenge. The questions include everything that can revolve around the defined *challenge*, including "*What problems are encountered in the user experience on the Apple Watch?*", "*Do the current Apple Watch apps provide a fulfilling user experience?*" and

"What is our user missing?"

Armed with the Apple Watch, we tested a number of third-party apps and *benchmarked them* against the system *apps* designed by Apple. We analysed statistical data available on the net and noticed that more than 80 per cent of Apple Watch users almost exclusively use only system *apps*, such as HEART RATE for heart activity monitoring, BREATH for relaxation or STOPWATCH for time management and stopwatches.

Therefore, through the essential questions and the activities carried out, we arrived at a summary of two observations that helped us to define a new *big idea* and a new *essential question*. We noticed in the segment of users defined as "pioneers" a lack of spirituality, due to their frenetic lifestyle, and in the "mature" segment of our users a propensity to use the Apple Watch *device* (which represents, in proper UX terms, our *touchpoint*) for activities to which they were accustomed with physical adjectives. Both users have a common denominator in their expectations regarding the use of the Apple Watch; they are looking for an immediate, simple, fast and incisive user experience. Practically speaking, it is not enough for the *app* to provide a single function, but this must be effected through a minimal interaction, lasting no more than a handful of seconds. A type of interaction that *Apple's Evangelism Team* has formalised under the term *Two Second Interaction*.

7.1.3. The synthesis phase

From these considerations, around the *big idea* "spirituality" was born the idea of an *app* that can help believers in praying the Holy Rosary. The choice of the Rosary is given by its intimate and confidential nature, a kind of introspective journey. Furthermore, the recitation of the Rosary involves the use of a very simple *set* of prayers and, not least, knowledge of the subject by

of the development *team* consisting mainly of Catholics and thus able to treat the subject matter with the proper respect and attention required ⁸⁰.

The choice of the Rosary, something widely known, from an application point of view presents an interesting challenge in that, although the individual prayers used in the recitation are universally known, their progression and overall structure of the Marian devotional prayer is almost unknown to many devout believers.

A whiteboard used during one of the many *brainstorming* sessions in the conception and development phases of the ROSARI UM - ROSARY CROWN application.

7.2. The UX design process

For the development of the user interaction, 'genius *design*' was used, considering the time available and the limited resources, in addition to the purely academic sphere: a method that affidrew on the *designer's* experience in defining the prerequisites. Thus, the context analysis i.e. the general strategy to be followed, the user needs, the identification of a *target group* and the *business* objectives were defined by me independently. Starting from

⁸⁰ At an early stage, the team had also considered a universal approach that could also deal with other religions such as Buddhism or Hinduism, but given the lack of knowledge on the subject, external consultations would have been necessary, which for reasons of time and budget were not feasible.

previous work experience in *retail*⁸¹ I tried to answer the question "*Who is the user of our app?*".

Based on my knowledge of Apple users, I was able to conclude that: the vast Apple Watch user base on the one hand consists of young pioneers, sporty, dynamic people with busy lives who use the device to do sports and quickly access notifications, and on the other hand, a more mature, health-conscious user base who uses the device primarily for health monitoring.

These considerations led me to define two *proto-personas*:

- *the pioneer*
- *the greeter*

For *testing*, a random audience was chosen consisting of fellow students, family members and friends who were only involved at the end of each iteration to test whether certain hypothesised functions or behaviours really worked as intended and, in accordance with the chosen development model, not to validate design choices.

7.2.1. Research and synthesis

After defining two reference *proto-personas*, the space in which the possible users move was assessed and the time factor was given utmost importance. Subsequently, an attempt was made to define an interaction lasting approximately two seconds within a mobility context. In this regard, it is also useful to analyse the environmental and cultural context in which our application comes to life and forms the backdrop to the user interaction: it is commonly considered uneducational to use electronic devices in a meditation context, perhaps in a church or even in other places where we find several people intent on the act of prayer.

As an *app* aimed at an audience of the faithful, it is also important to analyse the religious aspect. In this regard, we consulted Don Carmine, parish priest of Caserta, on the rituality of the Holy Rosary and research

⁸¹ From 2012 to 2019, I worked at R-STORE S. P. A. APPLE PREMIUM RESELLER as a technician and sales *specialist*. During that period, I had the opportunity to attend the APPLE WATCH product launch and get to know its users, their habits and difficulties of use.

personal acts in the official acts of the Vatican. Our research into recommended practices led us to consider the utterances made by Pope John Paul II:

"the crown used to record the succession of Hail Marys lends itself to expressing a symbolism that can give further depth to the contemplation [...] the crown extends its symbolic meaning to the reciprocal relationship, recalling with it the bond of communion and fraternity that binds us all a82".

So in carrying out the *task analysis* we have that our main goal: "to achieve a fulfilling user experience on the Apple Watch" and to achieve this we can define the sub-goals that we can list:

- achieve a *two second interaction*;
- not distract the user from its context;
- encourage meditation;
- help the faithful in the recitation of the Rosary.

At this stage I sought the collaboration of the *team* by organising *co-design* sessions. In this phase through *design thinking* techniques I guided the group in the process of generating new ideas. One of the techniques used was SCAMPER, aimed at providing seven different approaches to come up with innovative ideas and solutions ⁸³. The word SCAMPER is an acronym schematised in the following image:

⁸² I. PAULI PP. II SUMMI PONTEFICIS, *Epistula Apostolica - Rosarium Virginis Mariae*, 2002.

⁸³ B. EBERLE, *Scamper: Games for Imagination Development*, Prufrock Press Inc., 1996.

Illustrative image of the seven phases of the SCAMPER technique.

One of the first ideas to emerge from these sessions was the creation of a vocal Rosary to guide the user in its recitation. Although this initially found favour with the *team*, after a careful analysis of the context and of the prayer guides dictated by Karol Wojtyła, it seemed an inappropriate solution (just think of its use in a silent church at vespers time or of the mode of use which, through audio, would become passive and alienating, totally in contrast to an intimate context of concentration and meditation such as prayer).

7.2.2. Defining the user experience

Finally, based on the preceding considerations and carefully analysing the designated *touchpoint*, during a brainstorming session in which new proposals were constantly analysed and cyclically screened, we decided to base the user experience on the combination of man and machine. A digital-analogue interaction achieved by using one of the Apple Watch's own *input* devices: the *digital crown* which, typically rotated with index finger and thumb, reproduces exactly the *feeling* of the beads that make up the physical crown used for reciting the rosary.

A schematic raffiguration of the movement of the *digital crown*.

So the whole user experience is based on the fact that the digital crown of the Apple Watch becomes the beads of the Rosary and, by turning it, one switches from one prayer to another as in real life. *Haptic feedback* informs the user of the prayer transition, and on the device's *display* we can quickly see the main information, i.e. the prayer to be prayed at that moment, and in addition further information such as the Hail Mary count or the Mystery count.

7.3. The UI design process

For the design of the UI, once the user experience was defined and paper *sketches* created, analysing the context and in particular the symbols and colours of the Vatican State, I defined the colour palette, *type fonts* and we defined the logo.

The colour palette

The colour palette harking back to the symbols of Christianity and the Vatican uses a saturated yellow (HEX #DCCF26) as a distinctive colour that can refer both to yellow gold, in reference to the numerous golden sacred objects in use in churches, and to the yellow present on the flag of the Vatican State. The Apple Watch interfaces include, as guidelines, a background colour of absolute black (HEX #0000), in combination with pure white (HEX #FFFFFF), a light grey (HEX #9797) and a dark grey (HEX #333333) used at the

instead of black exclusively for *mockups* for the App Store, which, being viewed from the iPhone benefit from the use of a softer, non-absolute black for avoid *visual distortion* phenomena ⁸⁴ and visualisation problems to subjects astigmatics.

Colour palette chosen for application ROSARI UM - ROSARY CROWN .

The choice of typefaces

The choice of *font* used was strongly influenced by the context rather than by current trends. Nevertheless, the aim was to achieve an elegant result but at the same time convey solemnity, seriousness but without coming across as old and *démodé*.

The choice of font for titles and headlines first fell on the elegant TRAJAN ⁸⁵ font designed by designers Carol Twombly and Robert Slimbach and distributed under a paid use licence by Adobe, but then, for *budget* reasons, CINZEL ⁸⁶ font was used, designed by designer Natanael Gama and distributed free of charge by Google.

⁸⁴ T. ANTHONY, *Why You Should Never Use Pure Black for Text or Backgrounds*, (uxmovement.com 8 May 2018) [last accessed: 20.04.2020].

⁸⁵ (fonts.adobe.com/fonts/trajan)

⁸⁶ (fonts.google.com/specimen/Cinzel)

Logo design

The logo has evolved over time, always remaining faithful to the initial idea conceived during the *challenge* in analysis. The logo uses the entire colour palette, combining the concept of wheat (in English *bead*) with the symbol of Christianity par excellence which is the cross. All this is based on some of the basic principles of *gestalt* such as the principle of *good figure*, periodicity and induced movement.

Over time, *features were* added to change part of the logo. Specifically, the rays above the top of the cross. The first change effected was aimed at showing a greater connection with the Apple Watch device, transforming the triangular-shaped rays into rounded rectangles similar in shape to the markers on the 'analogue' watch dials. The second change was made after the *redesign* of the application by rewriting the *app* with SPRITEK EN ⁸⁷ to enhance the implementation of more fluid and believable animations, emphasising movement and dynamism.

Evolution of the logo from its creation in 2017 to the latest version in 2020.

⁸⁷ The *SpriteKit* framework simplifies the creation of high-performance, energy-efficient 2D games and animations.

7.7.1. Interface design

For the design of the interfaces, one of the main objectives was to reduce the cognitive load, i.e. to reduce as much as possible the mental effort required of the user who, let us remember, through an interaction with the product of just two seconds, must be able to obtain all the useful information. Hence a careful use of space and a reduction to a minimum of the information to be shown on the screen. Added to this is the desire to make interaction as comfortable as possible, and in this regard, some *feedback* from Apple Watch users expressing a sense of frustration when using certain *apps* was important. Analysing the *feedback*, in most cases the problems were generated by interacting with the device through touch *input*. We have therefore deliberately reduced interactions with the *display to a minimum*, relegating almost all interactions to the *digital crown*; the only action that is triggered by touch *input*, via *force touch*⁸⁸, is the activation of a service menu useful for example to pause prayer. A solution reminiscent of the *panic button*, found in physical interfaces and widely used in *industrial design*, which by its nature requires a strong intentionality in the action and is rarely activated randomly.

Apple Watch *app* interface declined for the two sizes and resolutions available in 2017.

In this phase, communication with the development *team* was important, and in this regard, it was important to provide the *software developer with* all the necessary information for the creation of the product as defined in the phases

⁸⁸ *Force Touch* is a technology developed by Apple Inc. that enables *trackpads* and *touchscreens* to distinguish between different levels of force applied to their surfaces.

of UX design and in the graphical modes expressed during the UI design phase.

It is important to make use of *wireframes* or *mock-ups*, commenting on them in order to provide all the required specifications. In the following I will show extracts from the documents used in the design phase in order to better clarify certain concepts. We will see the application of the colour palette and the description of two *micro-flows*, i.e. the interaction with the notification system and the *force touch* menu.

Here we see the interaction associated with the receipt of a notification.

A customised notification that is triggered at a certain time of day can be set up in the *app*. To this notification, the user can respond

with 'Start' starting the Rosary prayer immediately or 'Snooze' postponing the prayer until the next day. This very simple interaction, if not clarified well, leads to various possible criticalities since a *default notification* only has the 'Close' button marking the notification as read. This inhibits all other actions. Therefore, the *tasks* required by the developers will be as follows:

- Customise the notification.
- Provide two keys.
- Associate the *app's* open function with the 'Start' button.
- Create a function to postpone the notification by 24 hours.
- Associate the postpone function with the 'Snooze' button.

In this case, although the complexity of the task is very low, it required five *tasks* on the *software* development side, an annotated *design*, a few lines of text via *email* and a short verbal communication between *designer* and *software developer*.

Here we see the interaction related to the menu that can be called up via *force touch*.

Pressing hard on the display, i.e. using *force touch*, activates a menu that allows the prayer to be paused, resumed or the entire Rosary to be restarted. Even this simple interaction if not clarified and explained to the developer as described above can lead to misunderstandings. Firstly, there are three 'positive' actions, clearly in our example '*pause*', '*resume*' and '*restart*' but there is a fourth action called

"neutral" which is the "cancel" from which arises a simple question "What difference is there between "resume" and "cancel"?", "Does "cancel" by chance mean exit of the app? Why not use the term exit then?".

So a simple menu for controlling the *flow* of the *app* brings with it various questions that may also make one rethink certain processes and interactions. Starting from the initial definition of the purpose of this functionality and combining the considerations gathered from the questions raised by the view of this interface, one can think of redesigning the screen with only two buttons in this way.

Here we see the redesigned interaction.

7.4. Final delivery

The *deliverables*, just five days after the *challenge* was defined, were a documentation of the development process and a *beta* release of the application that was tested by the audience during the presentation that took place in front of course students, lecturers and Apple staff.

The *app*, from its private presentation at the Apple Developer Academy to its presentation to the general public a month later, garnered widespread approval, attracting the attention of numerous industry publications, the curiosity of numerous *bloggers*, and received the great accolade of being mentioned by Doug LeMoine, *senior designer at Apple*,

as an example of intentional *design* during a session ⁸⁹ of WWDC ⁹⁰ 2018 and being blessed by His Holiness Pope Francis.

A still from the recording of the '*Intentional Design*' session © 2018 Apple Inc.

A photo showing the Apostolic Blessing received by ROSARIUM .

⁸⁹ D. LEMOINE, *Intentional Design min. 37:00-38:30*, (developer.apple.com/videos/play/wwdc2018/802/) in *World Wide Developer Conference*, California, 2018.

⁹⁰ The Apple WorldWide Developers Conference is an annual conference held in California by Apple Inc. The conference is used by the company to showcase new products and technologies to developers, as well as offire hands-on workshops and *training* sessions.

6.5.1.Final considerations

The *UX design* process is a complex job that brings into play not only technical skills of an analytical and applicative nature, but also skills that affertain to the relational sphere, the *UX designer* figure demanded by the market, makes empathy a *mindset*, a cultural value and transfers its values to the final product, which, in addition to responding to ever-increasing needs in terms of innovation, is increasingly oriented towards satisfying real needs and concrete desires of users.

The *UX designer may* have strong roots in graphic design or industrial *design* but may also come from the field of cognitive sciences. In the French-speaking world in particular, almost all UXs have an academic *background in psychology* and rarely come from the technical world of graphic arts or engineering; but in its purest sense it is a figure who works at a high level of abstraction. He has the 'complete picture' of the project and is often the custodian of the product *vision* and is in charge of transferring it to the entire development *team*.

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LIST OF STANDARD ABBREVIATIONS

AA. VV.	various authors	o. c. / op. cit.	work cited
a.	year	ms., mss.	manuscript
a.c.d.	by	n., nn.	number, numbers
app.	appendix	n.s.	new series
art.	article	p., pp.	page, pages
art. cit-	article cited	par.	paragraph
approx.	approx.	rist.	reprint
ch.	chapter	riv.	revised
c., cc.	paper, cards	s. / ss.	following, following
cf. / cf.	compare	s.a.	without year
col.	column	s. d.	without date
coll.	necklace	sect.	section
doc.	document	ltd.	without a place
ed.	publisher	s.l.e.a.	without place and year
et al.	and others	s.l.e.n.a.	without place or year
e.g.	example	suppl.	suppling
file.	dossier	s.v.	under the heading
fig.	figure	tab.	table
f., ff.	sheet, sheet	table.	table
photogr.	photography	tit.	title
f.t.	out of text	translation.	translation
ill.	illustration	v., vv.	verse, verse
l.c.	place cited	see / see	refers to another publication with the same argumentation

LIST OF LATIN ABBREVIATIONS

EA. / EADEM	same	IIDEM	same authors
<i>Ib.</i> / <i>Ibid.</i> / <i>Ibid.</i>	in that same place	<i>passim</i>	here and there
ID., / IDEM	same author	<i>praesertim</i>	especially

LIST OF AUTHOR'S ABBREVIATIONS

UX	User Experience	ID	Industrial Design
EN	Information Technology	UXnet	User Experience Network
HCI	Human Computer Interaction	UCD	User-Centred Design
IxD	Interaction Design	UI	User Interface
MVP	Minimum Viable Product	AI	Information Architecture
UAT	User Acceptance Test	CBL	Challenge Based Learning
CBLD	Challenge Based Learning and Development	IDF	Interaction Design Foundation
ACOT2	Apple Classrooms of Tomorrow-Today	ACOT2	Apple Classrooms of Tomorrow-Today